

Human-centred generative AI framework for cultural industries' digital transition

Grant Agreement No 101178362

DELIVERABLE D1.1:

Context Understanding & Requirements Gathering R1

Work Package: WP1

LEAD BENEFICIARY:

Stichting Waag Society (WAAG)

Delivery Date: 30.9.2025

This project has received funding from the EU Horizon Research & Innovation programme under grant agreement No 101178362

Document Sheet

Project acronym	HAMLET
Project full title	A First of a kind Hub for circularity demonstrator for Attica and peripheral regions
Programme	Horizon Europe
Topic	HORIZON-CL2-2024-HERITAGE-01-03
Type of Action	HORIZON Innovation Actions
Grant Agreement	101178362
Start day	1 January 2025
Duration	36 months

LEGAL NOTICE

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HADEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

©HAMLET Consortium, 2025

Reproduction is authorised provided the source is acknowledged.

Document Information

Deliverable number	D1.1
Deliverable name	Context Understanding & Requirements Gathering.R1
Lead beneficiary	WAAG
WP	WP1
Related task(s)	T1.1 Context Understanding & Requirements Gathering
Type	R - Document, report
Dissemination Level	Public
Reviewers	Mert Akbal, Franziska Mair, Michael Schmitz, Jan Tretschok, Soenke Zehle, Sonia Alvez (HBKsaar), Dimitros Grigoriadis (HSRT), Anastasios Drosou, Giorgos Angelis (CERTH), Pourya Omid (WAAG)
Delivery date	30.9.2025
Main author(s)	Miha Tursic, Zoénie Liwen Deng (WAAG)
Contributor(s)	Ola Bonati (WAAG)

Document history

Version	Date	Changes	Reviewer/Contributor
V0.1	17.06.2025	Table of Contents and initial population	WAAG
V0.2	24.07.2025	First draft for peer review	WAAG
V0.3	5.09.2025	Second draft for peer review	CERTH
V0.4	22.09.2025	Final draft for peer review	WAAG, HBKsaar
V1	30.09.2025	Final document	WAAG

Publishable Summary

This deliverable presents the initial results of the HAMLET project's stakeholder engagement and requirement-gathering activities. It documents the conceptual, methodological, and empirical foundation for designing human-centred, value-driven AI tools for the cultural and creative industries (CCIs).

The report outlines the project's goals, guiding frameworks (including Value Sensitive Design and Critical Making), and an overview of relevant EU policy and standards. It presents findings from extensive stakeholder consultations-comprising interviews, a multi-partner survey, and co-creative workshops-which collectively informed the identification of 27 concerns, 22 value commitments, and 45 design requirements. These were cross-mapped to general and pilot-specific project goals to ensure alignment between stakeholder needs and project implementation.

The design requirements cover thematic clusters including human creativity and control, transparency and explainability, consent and governance, accessibility and inclusion, cultural specificity, sustainability, and creative interoperability. The report also details how these requirements respond to concerns such as automation, bias, loss of authorship, or platform dependency.

This document serves as a foundational reference for the technical design and development phases in WP1, WP2 and WP3 and will inform ongoing validation processes with end-users and pilot partners.

"This deliverable (D1.1 – Context Understanding & Requirements Gathering, Public Version) has undergone an ethical and GDPR compliance review as part of HAMLET's internal quality process. The document contains no personal data."

Table of Contents

1 Introduction.....	9
1.1 <i>HAMLET Project</i>	9
1.2 <i>Objectives of Context Understanding & Requirement Gathering</i>	9
1.3 <i>Deliverable Structure</i>	10
1.4 <i>Relationship with Other Deliverables</i>	10
2 Approach	10
2.1 <i>Challenges of generative AI in CCI</i>	11
2.2 <i>Methodology</i>	13
2.2.1 <i>Responsible AI for CCI Tool</i>	15
3 Stakeholders.....	16
4 Stakeholders Design Requirements	17
4.1 <i>Overview of Stakeholder Requirements</i>	17
4.2 <i>List of All Stakeholder Concerns, Values & Requirements</i>	19
4.2.1 <i>Concerns</i>	19
4.2.2 <i>Values</i>	21
4.2.3 <i>Design requirements</i>	23
4.3 <i>From the Pioneers to the Contemporaries of AI in CCI</i>	26
4.4 <i>Interviews with Experts</i>	30
4.5 <i>Workshops with Pilots and Enablers</i>	34
4.6 <i>Survey and Workshop with Stakeholders</i>	36
4.6.1 <i>Analysis Methodology</i>	37
4.6.2 <i>Results from the Survey and Workshop</i>	38
5 Demographics.....	40
6 Conclusion & next steps	42
References	44
Annex #1: From the Pioneers to the Contemporaries of AI in CCI.....	Error! Bookmark not defined.
<i>Global Pioneers of Algorithmic & Early AI Art</i>	Error! Bookmark not defined.
<i>Contemporary AI Art</i>	Error! Bookmark not defined.
Annex #2: Interviews with Experts	Error! Bookmark not defined.
Annex #3: Design Requirements from Pilots and Enablers	Error! Bookmark not defined.
<i>Pilot 1 - Causa Creations: Human-AI Collaborative Game Design</i>	Error! Bookmark not defined.
<i>Pilot 2 - Chimera Entertainment: Budget-Restrained Game Development</i>	Error! Bookmark not defined.
<i>Pilot 3 - ICK Dans: Archetype Alchemy</i>	Error! Bookmark not defined.
<i>Pilot 4 - IJAD: Phygital Theatre</i>	Error! Bookmark not defined.
<i>Enabler 2.1 - Generic Procedural Content Generation (CERTH)</i>	Error! Bookmark not defined.

Enabler 2.2 - Data-Driven Cultural Content Adaptation (CERTH)..... Error! Bookmark not defined.
Enabler 2.3 - Cross-Domain Audience Engagement Analytics (TAA)..... Error! Bookmark not defined.
Enabler 2.4 - Enabler Integration Agent (CERTH)..... Error! Bookmark not defined.
Enabler 3.1 - Dance Style Analysis and Generation (CYENS) Error! Bookmark not defined.
Enabler 3.2 - Music-to-Movement Translation Enabler for Dance (AUTH) Error! Bookmark not defined.
Enabler 3.3 - Immersive Design Integration Enabler for Dance & Theatre (CYENS) Error! Bookmark not defined.
Enabler 3.4 - Adaptive Narrative Enabler for Games & Theatre (Causa Creations) Error! Bookmark not defined.
Annex #4: Stakeholder Requirements Survey & Workshop..... Error! Bookmark not defined.
Survey..... Error! Bookmark not defined.
Survey results Error! Bookmark not defined.
Workshop results Error! Bookmark not defined.

List of Figures

Figure 1. Responsible Ai for CCI Tool.....	15
Figure 2: a) Gordon Pask, <i>Musicolor</i> (1953), b) Nicolas Schöffer, <i>CYSP -1</i> (1956), c) Martin Graetz, Wayne Wiitanen, Bob Saunders, Steve Piner, <i>Spacewar!</i> (1962), d) (1956), Vera Molnár, <i>Interruptions</i> (1968), e) Jeanne Beaman and Paul le Vasseur, <i>Random Dances</i> (1968), f) Harold Cohen <i>AARON</i> (1972-2010), g) Karl Sims, <i>Evolved Virtual Creatures</i> (1994), h) Anna Ridler, <i>Mosaic Virus</i> (2018), i) Fig. 9: Kate Crawford and Vladan Joler, <i>Anatomy of an AI System</i> (2018).....	27
Figure 3. Geographical representation.....	41
Figure 4. Gender diversity.	41
Figure 5. Occupational status.	42

List of Tables

Table 1: General project goals.....	11
Table 2: Pilot and Enabler specific project goals.	12
Table 3: Categories of Stakeholders.	16
Table 4: Stakeholder roles per each HAMLET sector, gaming, theatre, dance and general.	16
Table 5: General stakeholder's concerns about AI in CCI.....	20
Table 6: General stakeholder's values underlying AI in CCI.	22
Table 7: All stakeholder requirements based on all the previous chapters.....	23
Table 8: Design requirements based on the literacy review of global pioneer sand contemporary AI in CCI.	29
Table 9: Design requirements based on interviews with experts.	32
Table 10: Design requirements based on the workshops with Pilots and Enablers.	34
Table 11: General stakeholder requirements from the survey and workshop.	39
Table 12: Design requirements based on global pioneers of algorithmic and AI art. Error! Bookmark not defined.	
Table 13: Design requirements based on contemporary AI art. Error! Bookmark not defined.	
Table 14: Design requirements based on interviews with experts. Error! Bookmark not defined.	
Table 15: General design requirements based on pilot's and enabler's use cases. Error! Bookmark not defined.	
Table 16: Design requirements based on pilot's and enabler's use case specific creative and technical challenges, and concerns. Error! Bookmark not defined.	

Abbreviations

Abbreviations	Full name
AI	Artificial Intelligence
Causa Creations	Causa Creations Interactive Media GmbH
CCIs	Cultural and Creative Industries
CERTH	ETHNIKO KENTRO EREVNAS KAI TECHNOLOGIKIS ANAPTYXIS
Chimera	Chimera Entertainment
C	Concerns
CYENS CoE	CYENS Centre of Excellence
DR	Design Requirements
GAI	Generative Artificial Intelligence
HAMLET	Human-centred generative AI framework for cultural industries' digital Transition
HBKsaar	Hochschule der Bildenden Künste Saar
HSRT	HYPERTech KENTRO EPISTIMONIKON KAI TECHNOLOGIKON EREVNON AEIFORIAS ASTIKI MI KERDOSKOPIKI ETAIREIA
ICK	Stichting International Choreographic Arts Center
IJAD	IJAD Dance Company
Imperial	Imperial College London
TAA	The Audience Agency
V	Values
WAAG	Stichting Waag Society
WPx	Work Package number x
Dx.x	Deliverable number x.x
Tx.x	Task x.x

1 Introduction

1.1 HAMLET Project

HAMLET (Human-centred generative AI fraMework for culturaL industriEs' digital Transition) is a Horizon Europe Innovation Action that aims to democratise generative AI technologies for Europe's cultural and creative industries (CCIs). The project brings together technologists, artists, designers, and researchers to shape a human-centred digital transition in the cultural sector.

This Ethics Manual defines the ethical principles, procedures, and oversight mechanisms that guide the HAMLET's research and innovation activities. It ensures that all work carried out in the project is in compliance with EU legal, regulatory, and ethical frameworks, throughout the research, development, deployment, and dissemination phases.

Special emphasis is placed on areas specific to generative AI and the cultural domain, including transparency, fairness, inclusion, data provenance, human oversight, intellectual property, and algorithmic accountability.

1.2 Objectives of Context Understanding & Requirement Gathering

This document delivers "D1.1 Context Understanding and Requirement Gathering" from the "Work package WP1 - Human-Centred Enabler Design" lead by project partner "CERTH". This document is categorized as a public report to be delivered of the month 6 (31.6.2025) of the project, while being postponed to month 9 (31.9.2025).

Understanding the wider context of GAI in CCI and related stakeholder requirements is one of the pillars of the HAMLET project. For the project to develop user-centric framework tailored to the unique needs of the CCIs, this "Stakeholder Requirement Report" focuses on a detailed exploration of the ethical, cultural, societal, and technological aspects influencing technology adoption within CCIs. By engaging directly with users and stakeholders, D1.1 captures a diverse range of perspectives and requirements, translating these insights into actionable guidelines for technologists. This ensures that the framework not only meets the practical needs of users but also aligns with broader ethical and cultural values, thereby fostering a technology ecosystem that builds on responsible innovative.

Therefore, the purpose of this "Stakeholder Requirement Report" is to contribute to:

- Designing and implementing a user-friendly AI for CCI framework, based on the actual needs and requirements of creatives and artists, for the human-centered and ethical digital transition of the CCIs through the uptake and use of novel AI and conventional tools.
- Ensuring the exploitation of the HAMLET framework and tools while ensuring the uptake of project results and requirements by the main CCI stakeholders.
- Building on public cultural values as defined through collaborative research together with project partners and identified stakeholders.
- Recognizing sensitivities of each AI for CCI use-case (project related and beyond) which require more inclusive and open design approach, allowing critical user interventions also into the development phase.
- Assuring adoption of project results by building trust between users and developers, as concerns into AI influence decisions for technology adoption.

This report is a living document. It will be reviewed and updated in response to project developments, emerging risks, stakeholder feedback, and relevant changes in law or ethical norms. Updates will be overseen by the Ethics Committee.

1.3 Deliverable Structure

Task 1.1 explores a variety of AI and GAI related ethical, cultural, societal, and technological concerns as foundations for the design and development of the HAMLET framework and translate them into stakeholder needs and requirements. WAAG organised interviews, public events, collaborative workshops, survey, discussions with creative professionals and artists with whom the landscape of concerns and aspirations related to AI in CCI was mapped. Following the established overview and together with engaged stakeholders, this task formulates their expectations and preferences. The gathered insights are synthesized into a comprehensive set of stakeholder design requirements, offering clear, actionable guidance for the development of HAMLET's user-centric technologies.

This specific report is structured to provide a transparent and actionable guide to the stakeholder requirements of the HAMLET project. It is designed to align with both Horizon Europe requirements and the specific objectives of HAMLET's innovation agenda in generative AI and cultural industries. Therefore, the document is divided into the following core sections:

- **Section 1 - Introduction:** provides the scope of this deliverable in detail, its relationship with other deliverables and a brief description of the deliverable's structure.
- **Section 2 - Approach:** introducing general challenges of AI in CCI and selection of methodology that addresses these challenges in way results contribute to the project objectives; while providing Responsible AI for CCI Tool for CCI stakeholders to decide how to engage with AI or GAI.
- **Section 3 - Stakeholders:** detailed categories and types of stakeholders as relevant to this project.
- **Section 4 - Stakeholder design requirements:** an extensive study into GAI system requirements based on the insights from the history of AI in CCI, in-depth insights from practitioners and experts, project related partners and wider CCI ecosystem.
- **Section 5 - Demographics:** quantitative background of engaged stakeholders.
- **Section 6 - Conclusion:** summary of stakeholder requirements and description of next steps.

1.4 Relationship with Other Deliverables

This Stakeholder Requirement Report is closely linked to several deliverables mainly under **WP1: Human-Centred Enabler Design**, as well as **WP6: AI Ethics, Community Building and policy making for the CCIs** which provide both upstream guidance for design, development and impact assessment activities. The following reports serve as key references:

- **D1.2 Use cases definition & Application scenarios. R1**
- **D6.3 Impact of AI Ethics in Cultural, Creative & Art Practice**
- **D6.6 Virtual Living Lab setup & community building**

2 Approach

The HAMLET project is approaching the question of GAI in CCI from in a very "Hamletian way," building on a sequence of questions "AI or not AI? & If AI, then how?" Such "existential" struggle is a common question for today's creatives and artists at their everyday decisions. Focusing on the moment of their "existential" making of creative, operational and business decisions, this report is not only providing answers on *how to*

adopt GAI into CCI practices, but how to form decisions for responsible design, development and use of GAI in CCI.

2.1 Challenges of generative AI in CCI

This overarching challenge calls for a system design approach that goes beyond utilitarian or purely technical considerations. Its objectives require **embedding ethical reflection, participatory design, and stakeholder responsiveness into operations from the outset**-affirming that *what* technologies do cannot be separated from *why* they exist, and by and for *whom* they are built. This demands a value-, concern-, and user-driven methodology in which non-functional requirements such as fairness, inclusivity, and transparency are not treated as secondary add-ons but as foundational design constraints shaping the core functionalities themselves (OO#1, OO#3, OO#4). It further requires iterative, real-world testing and refinement, guided by the lived experiences and concerns of those directly affected-not only those who benefit (OO#6)-while engaging broader cultural, legal, and political frameworks to ensure long-term relevance and responsible uptake (OO#7).

Table 1: General project goals.

ID	Goal	Description	Why (C, V)	How (DR)
G01	Human-centred & Ethical Digital Transition	Develop a user-friendly framework grounded in actual needs of creators.	C01, C02; V01, V02, V04	DR01, DR02, DR03, DR04, DR05, DR06, DR07, DR08, DR09, DR10, DR12, DR23, DR24, DR25, DR32, DR37
G02	User-driven Framework	Design and implement the framework based on user needs and requirements, with iterative evaluation.	C01, C13; V02, V04, V13	DR01, DR02, DR03, DR04, DR05, DR06, DR07, DR09, DR10, DR12, DR23, DR24, DR25, DR30
G03	Collaborative Community Hub	Provide a single interaction point for enablers and Hub, using user-driven design for seamless interaction.	C17, C21; V04, V07	DR05, DR08, DR12, DR13, DR14, DR15, DR17, DR18, DR20, DR21, DR22, DR25, DR32, DR33, DR35, DR36, DR37, DR41, DR42, DR43, DR44, DR45
G04	Suite of AI Enablers	Produce sophisticated AI enablers demonstrating framework efficacy, creativity, and interoperability.	V04, V19	DR01, DR02, DR03, DR04, DR05, DR06, DR09, DR10, DR12, DR14, DR15, DR16, DR19, DR20, DR23, DR24, DR25, DR30, DR35
G05	Pilot Validated Framework	Conduct a thorough validation of the framework, using enablers and testing them in in real-world pilot cases that tackle actual needs and issues.	C21, V11	DR04, DR05, DR06, DR09, DR10, DR14, DR15, DR16, DR17, DR25, DR39, DR43
G06	Framework Exploitation	Ensure the exploitation of the HAM-LET framework and tools.	C18; V04, V19	DR01, DR02, DR03, DR04, DR05, DR06, DR09, DR10, DR12, DR14, DR15, DR16, DR19, DR20, DR23, DR24, DR25, DR30, DR35, DR39, DR40, DR41

G07	Support Smaller CCI Entities	Address barriers such as costs, funding, technical gaps, and platform dependency for dance/theatre & games.	C21; V11, V19	DR04, DR05, DR06, DR09, DR10, DR14, DR15, DR16, DR17, DR19, DR20, DR23, DR24, DR25, DR30, DR35, DR39, DR43
G08	Integration of Ethical AI Practices	Respect artistic integrity, cultural diversity, and ethical standards in AI adoption.	C06, C09; V12, V20	DR03, DR12, DR18, DR19, DR22, DR33, DR34, DR36, DR37, DR38, DR40, DR42, DR44
G09	Cross-sector Extensibility	Ensure scalability of framework beyond performing arts and games to other CCIs.	C11; V18, V19	DR04, DR05, DR06, DR09, DR10, DR14, DR15, DR16, DR19, DR20, DR23, DR24, DR30, DR35
G10	Sustainability & Green Digital Transition	Prioritise energy-efficient AI, aligned with Green Deal & NEB values.	C09, C18; V22, V20	DR03, DR12, DR18, DR22, DR23, DR24, DR33, DR34, DR36, DR38, DR39, DR40, DR41, DR42, DR44
G11	Cultural and Societal Impact	Enhance accessibility, safeguard diversity and heritage, and foster inter-cultural understanding.	C07, C27; V07, V14	DR04, DR11, DR21, DR22, DR31, DR37, DR42

As the core validation of the HAMLET framework will take place through predefined real-world pilots (G05), the specific goals of these Pilots provide concrete stakeholder use cases that guide the co-design and co-development of the enablers.

Table 2: Pilot and Enabler specific project goals.

ID	Goal	Description	Why (Concerns, Values)	How (DR)
PG01	Choreographic Sequences	Revolutionize choreography by analysing styles and generating new dance sequences.	C01, C05, C24; V01, V03, V20	DR01, DR02, DR03, DR06, DR07, DR08, DR12, DR18, DR26, DR27, DR28, DR32, DR33, DR34, DR36, DR37, DR40, DR42, DR44
PG02	Music to Movement	Translate musical structures and features into movement patterns, supporting expressive dance and theatre.	C05, C23; V03, V20	DR03, DR12, DR13, DR18, DR26, DR27, DR28, DR33, DR34, DR36, DR40, DR42, DR43, DR44
PG03	Narrative Development	Enhance narrative development in theatre and games, enabling dynamic and interactive storytelling.	C04, C03, C16; V03, V15, V20	DR03, DR08, DR11, DR12, DR18, DR19, DR26, DR27, DR28, DR29, DR30, DR31, DR32, DR33, DR34, DR36, DR40, DR42, DR44
PG04	Audience Engagement	Capture, analyse, and integrate audience responses and social media trends into performances.	C10, C11, C24; V06, V07, V20	DR03, DR04, DR11, DR12, DR18, DR20, DR21, DR22, DR33, DR34, DR35, DR36, DR40, DR42, DR44

PG05	Phyigital Experience	Bridge lives and digital performance through XR/VR, providing new immersive audience experiences.	C22, C23; V09, V18, V20	DR03, DR08, DR12, DR13, DR18, DR20, DR33, DR34, DR35, DR36, DR40, DR42, DR43, DR44
PG06	Game Asset Generation	Automate creation of game assets (characters, items, scenes), accelerating development and reducing costs.	C03, C08, C13; V01, V15, V12	DR01, DR06, DR07, DR08, DR11, DR19, DR29, DR30, DR31, DR32, DR33, DR36, DR37, DR38, DR42
PG07	Cultural Resonance	Ensure that generated game assets and narratives are culturally resonant and context-specific.	C14, C15, C16; V16, V15, V10	DR11, DR19, DR29, DR30, DR31, DR32, DR33, DR34
PG08	Conversational Interface	Provide a conversational interface for integrating multiple enablers seamlessly into creative workflows.	C05, C22, C23; V06, V14, V18	DR13, DR20, DR21, DR22, DR31, DR35, DR43, DR44

All these goals build on the understanding that *technologies are never neutral*; they embed the values, assumptions, and power dynamics of those who create and deploy them. Generative AI, in particular, has become a focal point of controversy-raising urgent questions about authorship, bias, and the appropriation of cultural and creative labour. Conventional system design, which separates functional from non-functional requirements, often frames functionality as objective while relegating ethical and social concerns to the margins. In practice, however, qualities such as explainability, sustainability, and cultural sensitivity are inseparable from system behaviour: they determine not only how technologies function but also who benefits, who is excluded, and what risks are reproduced. For instance, the capacity of generative AI to generate content cannot be meaningfully specified without addressing issues of data ownership, artistic intent, cultural context, and potential harm.

2.2 Methodology

Grounded in frameworks like **Value Sensitive Design**¹ and Bruno Latour’s notion of “**matters of concern**,”² HAMLET takes these dynamics as central, framing technologies not as neutral tools but as socially negotiated infrastructures that should remain open to controversy, reflection, and collective redefinition. System Design approach with questions of «*How the system should behave?*» and «*What the system must do?*» is here foregrounded by Value Sensitive Design questions «*What values are implicated in design?*», «*Are there any value tensions?*» and «*What assumptions are embedded into system’s design or purpose?*» However, due to the low experience and previous adoption of GAI in CCI stakeholders lack concrete relation to these technologies, for which Critical Making provides additional questions that help providing required insights asking «*What assumptions underly the technology?*», «*Who is included or excluded?*», «*What can fail?*» and «*What materials, systems, infrastructures are used?*»

The effort of mapping stakeholders and their requirements builds on:

¹ Friedman, Batya, Peter H. Kahn Jr., and Alan Borning. “Value Sensitive Design and Information Systems.” In *Human-Computer Interaction in Management Information Systems: Foundations*, edited by Ping Zhang and Dennis Galletta, 348–372. Armonk, NY: M.E. Sharpe, 2006.

² Latour, Bruno. 2004. “Why Has Critique Run Out of Steam? From Matters of Fact to Matters of Concern.” *Critical Inquiry* 30 (2): 225–248. <https://doi.org/10.1086/421123>.

- What are existing concerns of CCI in regard to GAI?
- What are the values not only in GAI use, but also in its design and development?
- How can concerns and values be translated into operational context of GAI? What are the processes and roles supporting implementation of these translations?
- How can concerns and values of newly developed GAI technologies and tools be tested and validated?

HAMLET's stakeholder requirement methodology addresses these questions in few steps:

1. **Understanding state of the art of existing concerns and values** through literacy review of the history of AI in CCI, interviews with experts, online survey and stakeholder workshop, and Pilots and Enablers as experienced users.
2. **Stakeholder mapping and clustering** based on their role connected to design, development or use of GAI in CCI; with the focus on the process of making decisions.
3. **Engagement with stakeholders** and collecting their use cases on their engagement with GAI, their concerns in relation to their practice, their undelaying values, and asking for requirements on concrete operational and actionable proposals.
4. **Analysis of stakeholder input.**
5. **Translation of stakeholder input into Stakeholder Design Requirements (SDR).**

Addressing the challenges of designing, developing and using GAI in CCI, Waag explores stakeholder design requirements with its four core methodologies: Public Stack,³ Users as Designers,⁴ Critical Making,⁵ and Art-driven innovation.⁶

- The Public Stack explores technologies through Value Sensitive Design in collaborative way, **defining values shared between the stakeholders.**
- With Users as Designers approach, Waag **positions users in a role of designing use-case-specific requirements** which require more open innovation process.
- The Critical Making approach **critically explores the broader context of GAI in CCI**, examining key concerns, sensitivities, and controversies to ensure they are addressed in a way that maintain boundaries and fosters greater trust in the project's final outcomes.
- Art-driven innovation approach provides **guidelines for collaborative research, exploration, design and development**, led by creative and art actors.

Such an approach provides not so much of a fixed set of requirements but more of **a tool for users to engage with GAI for CCI in responsible way-HAMLET Responsible AI for CCI Tool**. As GAI technologies are so

³ Link: <https://publicstack.net>

⁴ Link: <https://waag.org/en/project/users-designers/>

⁵ Link: <https://waag.org/en/article/role-critical-making/>

⁶ Link: <https://betterfactory.eu/new-sme-artist-collaboration-guide-launched-by-better-factory-to-transform-european-manufacturing/>

rapidly changing, this tool enables users to learn, question, refine, and negotiate the adoption of GAI according to their case specific use. Waag understands the challenge of this adoption as akin to *Hamlet's existential question-what constitutes responsible AI in CCIs, and how can it be innovated responsibly?*

The aim of HAMLET Responsible AI for CCI Tool is thus to support creative professionals and artists in deciding how to engage with and utilise AI enablers in their concrete creative, cultural, or artistic practices.

2.2.1 Responsible AI for CCI Tool

Figure 1. Responsible Ai for CCI Tool

This tool is getting developed throughout the HAMLET project as an open guideline for CCI stakeholders to responsibly decide on the design, development and use of GAI in CCI. This effort acknowledges that CCI stakeholders are not solely users but also designers and developers of AI solutions.

The guideline provides:

- **Literature review of AI in CCI** providing insights into the legacy of arts and creativity in developing computer, digital and AI arts throughout the 20th century.
- **Mapping stakeholders** identifying users and creators, organisations, experts such as ethicists and legal advisors, technologists, policy makers, and funding bodies.
- **Interviews with experts and practitioners** providing insights from variety of research and practice-based work about and with AI in CCI.
- **Workshops between creative and technical partners** providing comparative discussion between creative and technical challenges while also addressing concerns into AI in CCI.
- **Wider stakeholder surveys** providing geographical and sectoral trends of Ai in CCI.

This tool is **for technology developers who want to create AI solutions with and for creatives**, which include research projects and SMEs that strive for responsible and relevant technologies. We invite you to start with the question: AI, or not? Instead of following the hype of AI, those who want to develop technological tools to assist creative works in CCI need to first ask: is there any existing open-source algorithmic or AI tools that can fulfil the identified needs? Or do the Big Tech AI platforms satisfy these needs, but they violate privacy and have many ethical and environmental issues? If there is no existing ethical open-source tools, and we don't want to opt for Big Tech's problematic platforms, then yes, let's make a responsible AI tool for CCI.

To ensure the technologies that will be created will be of relevance to stakeholders, we recommend to follow this guideline above to conduct pre-development research. Below is a brief explanation.

1. **Literature review of AI in CCI:** In order to understand what has been done in the intersection of digital technology and the chosen CCI field, we recommend to make a brief literature review that covers the significant innovations.

2. **Mapping stakeholders:** In order to make technologies that are relevant for users and creators, we recommend to not only to map out categories of individuals, but also identify organisations that might use these technologies, ethicists and legal advisors who can help to ensure the process and end products are ethical and legal, technologists who are capable to realise the project, and policy makers and funding bodies who may want to support such projects.
3. **Interviews with experts and practitioners:** After mapping stakeholders, we recommend to conduct in-depth interviews with experts and practitioners in the field to understand the methods, the needs, the concerns, the possible pitfalls, and the ethical implications.
4. **Workshops between creative and technical partners:** Involve the end users at the very beginning. If this is a company working on development of new technologies, we recommend to invite some of the creatives that have been interviewed and who have shown strong interests as collaborative partners to a series of workshop. If this is a research project, we recommend the technical partners and creative partners together to conduct workshops. The goal of the workshops is to co-create the challenges and collaborative process.
5. **Wider stakeholder surveys:** In order to gather information about wider potential users about their thoughts and feelings about AI tools in CCI, we recommend to create a survey and spread it broadly across geographies.

3 Stakeholders

Initial stakeholder mapping was organised as a workshop between project partners, exploring their concrete CCI ecosystems. The result are five categories & types of stakeholders.

Table 3: Categories of Stakeholders.

Category	Type	Examples
Primary	Users and Creators	Artists, game developers, choreographers
Secondary	Organizations	Theatres, studios, CCI SMEs, CCIs networks
Tertiary	Experts	Ethical/legal advisors, HCD experts
Enablers	Technologists	AI developers, platform architects
Policy & Impact	Policy makers, Funding bodies	EC and national policymakers, decision makers

Table 4: Stakeholder roles per each HAMLET sector, gaming, theatre, dance and general.

Category	Roles	Approached
Primary stakeholders in gaming sector	Game Designer, Programmer / Developer, Narrative Designers / Writers, Visual Artists, Animator, Level Designer, Audio Designer, Interface Designer	Interviews, Survey, Pilots
Primary stakeholders in dance sector	Artistic Director, Choreographer, Dancer, Creative Technologist	Interviews, Survey, Pilots
Primary stakeholders in theatre sector	Director, Dramaturgist, Actor, Creative Technologist	Interviews, Survey, Pilots
Primary stakeholders in media art sector	Critical Makers, Creative Coder, Artistic Researcher	Interviews, Survey
Primary stakeholders in theatre and dance technical roles	Lighting designer, Costume designer, Stage manager, Set designer, Sound designer	Survey
End-users	Audience / Visitor, Gamer, Modder, Streamer	Survey

Secondary stakeholders in gaming sector	Manager, Producer / Project Manager, Marketing / Communication officer, Community Engagement	Survey, Pilots
Secondary stakeholders in dance and theatre sector	Manager, Producer, Marketing / Communication officer, Community Engagement	Survey, Pilots
Secondary ecosystem	CCI network (S+T+ARTS, EIT), Game Publisher, Cultural Organization, Cultural Agency, Academy, Student, Creative Technology Studio, Media Lab, Artist Union, Digital Activist	Interviews, Events, Survey
Tertiary stakeholders	Researcher / Theorist (Game, Dance, Theatre, Cultural), Ethicist, Social studies scholar, Legal expert	Interviews, Survey
Enabling stakeholders	AI developer, platform architect, Gaming platform, Distribution platform, Theatre & Dance festival, AI developer, LLM provider, XR, VR developer	Enablers, Survey
Policy	Funding organization, Lawmaker, Policymaker	Survey

4 Stakeholders Design Requirements

This chapter gathers stakeholder design requirements by following the methodology explained above. Rather than focusing on functional and non-functional requirements for each technology, the SDR are concern and value driven while addressing specific CCI sectors and trans-sectorial.

4.1 Overview of Stakeholder Requirements

The design requirements emerging from the HAMLET stakeholder engagement process are grounded in a broad range of concerns (Table 8) and values (Table 9) expressed by artists, technologists, cultural practitioners, and sector-specific experts across the Creative and Cultural Industries (CCIs). They collectively articulate a vision for AI that enhances rather than displaces creative work, and that remains aligned with diverse ethical, cultural, and embodied practices.

- Human-Centred Creativity and Control:** Creative stakeholders across domains consistently emphasized the need for AI to augment, not replace creativity (DR01-DR05). Artists want to remain in control, using AI to assist with mundane tasks or open new directions-but not to define the artistic voice. As Harold Cohen famously asked: “If AARON makes the drawing, who is the artist?” Game designer Sam Liberty cautioned against AI being used to produce “good enough” content at scale, undermining the value of artistic quality and authorship. At the core of stakeholder concerns is the need for AI systems to respect creative autonomy and authorship (C01, C02, C04, C05). Requirements such as Human-Centred Creativity (DR01), Human-in-the-Loop Creative Control (DR02), and Alignment with Artistic Intentions (DR03) ensure that AI tools do not override but instead amplify human creativity, enabling artists to direct, refine, or reject outputs in line with their aesthetic and cultural goals. These requirements reflect values such as Creativity, Authorship, Authenticity (V01), Creative Autonomy (V02), and Meaningful Collaboration (V04).
- Transparency, Explainability and Ethical Infrastructure:** Several design requirements (DR06-DR10) demand that AI systems be legible, explainable, and trustworthy, with logic and processes visible to users and audiences alike. Inspired by pioneers like Manfred Mohr and Harold Cohen, designers should “reveal

underlying logic, parameters, and rulesets.” Interviewees like Abdelhadi Baaddi and Matjaz Vidmar emphasized the need for locally hosted, interpretable tools that avoid black-box infrastructures. Stakeholders expressed deep concern over the opacity of AI systems (C21), potential misuse of creative data (C06, C09), and over-reliance on black-box models (C12). In response, requirements such as Transparent, Interpretable Outputs (DR14), Explainability (DR15), Make Rule Systems & Logic Transparent (DR16), and Reveal System Infrastructure & Power Relations (DR18) aim to open the inner workings of generative systems to scrutiny, oversight, and contestation. These are grounded in the values of Openness, Trust, Transparency (V11), Reflectivity & Critical Thinking (V19), and Responsibility & Care (V20).

- **Pluralism, Cultural Sensitivity, and Non-Mainstream Outputs:** Stakeholders warned that AI tools risk flattening diverse voices unless trained with sensitivity to cultural, gendered, and epistemic difference (DR11-DR14). Elio Steffen warned that default models often erase queer and disabled bodies, reinforcing normativity. Echoing this, Dr. Phaedra Shanbaum noted: “Data collection is never neutral-one must ask: who is this data about?” Generative AI must not reinforce existing cultural hierarchies or homogenize artistic practices. Several DRs specifically address the risks of cultural bias (C13), marginalization (C07-C09), and flattening of meaning (C10, C14). Requirements such as Embed Cultural Context & Non-Western Frameworks (DR29), Expose & Address Cultural Biases (DR30), Challenge Normativity & Queer the Dataset (DR31), and Non-Mainstream Outputs (DR32) reinforce values of Inclusivity (V14), Diversity (V15), and Cultural Respect, Sensitivity & Specificity (V16). Together, they ensure that generative tools serve a multiplicity of worldviews, bodies, and creative vocabularies.
- **Embodiment, Situated Use, and Sensory Engagement:** Creative professionals-especially in theatre, dance, and performance-call for AI tools to support live, bodily, and sensory engagement (DR15-DR20). As Prof. Kristina Höök stated, “intelligence is inseparable from embodiment.” AI systems should work with lived experience, not abstract it away. Mime artist Niek Vanosterweyck emphasized the importance of glitch and feedback as creative stimuli, rejecting seamless automation. Participants across dance, performance, and storytelling domains consistently called for systems that engage with the body, environment, and temporality of live artistic practice. This cluster includes Support Embodied & Sensory Interaction (DR37), Enable Situated, Embodied, & Contingent Interaction (DR38), and Embodied Dialogue (DR39). These requirements address concerns over disembodiment and the loss of lived experience (C25), and are aligned with Artistic Authenticity (V03), Situated Knowledge (V17), and Emotional Depth (V10).
- **Experimentation, Improvisation, and Generativity:** Generative AI systems should not be deterministic. Instead, they must foster improvisation, chance, and open-ended exploration (DR21-DR25). Vera Molnár championed the balance between control and randomness: “I come up with a system... it’s an experimental method, step by step.” Ernest Edmonds underscored feedback loops in generative art as key to discovery and learning. Rather than rigid automation, stakeholders emphasized the need for AI systems to support improvisation, emergence, and serendipity. Requirements such as Support Playfulness & Improvisation (DR11), Embrace Randomness & Generativity (DR10), and Foster Speculative & Critical Imagination (DR09) are designed to keep creative processes open-ended. They respond to concerns around over-standardisation (C23), creative stagnation, and lack of surprise, and are grounded in Playfulness (V09), Freedom (V05), and Reflectivity and Critical Thinking (V19).
- **Consent, Ownership, and Data Governance:** Interviewees across disciplines raised urgent concerns about data ethics, consent, IP, and control over creative inputs and outputs (DR26-DR31). Flavia Dzodan and Matjaz Vidmar both insisted on opt-out mechanisms and recognition of dataset labour. Anna Ridler stated: “A dataset is creative work and becomes an artwork in and of itself.” Ensuring control over data, representations, and synthetic outputs is essential to protecting creative labour. Several DRs address

concerns about lack of consent (C01), unresolved IP (C02, C09), and platform dependency (C18). Requirements such as Data Governance & Consent (DR36), Support Consent & Voice Ownership (DR37), Build Conditions for Consent & Opt-Out Mechanisms (DR38), and Protected Creative Environment (DR42) uphold the values of Ownership (V06), Fairness (V12), and Sovereignty (V22).

- **Access, Education, and Interoperability:** AI should be accessible to all—regardless of technical background, ability, or economic means (DR32-DR35). Game technologist Lazaros Vrysis noted the need for “human-in-the-loop” systems that also support non-programmers. Barriers to entry—technical, linguistic, or infrastructural—remain a serious concern (C07, C27). Requirements like Democratize Access & Reduce Technical Barriers (DR18), Accessibility & Mutability (DR19), AI Literacy & Education (DR33), and Technical Interoperability (DR44) directly address this, enabling broader, more equitable use of AI tools across sectors. These reflect values such as Accessibility (V07), Adaptability (V08), and Ethical AI Use (V18).
- **Public, Participatory and Sustainable AI:** Finally, participants critiqued corporate dependency, advocating for public, open, and decentralized alternatives to commercial AI (DR36-DR40). Vidmar and Baaddi both called for “local models” and AI as “civic infrastructure.” The stakeholder vision points to AI as a civic and public infrastructure—shared, transparent, accountable. Requirements like Model AI as Public, Participatory Infrastructure (DR45), Foster Data Sovereignty (DR41), and Decentralize Infrastructure (DR40) suggest a structural rethinking of AI development and deployment. These DRs respond to systemic concerns around environmental cost (C19), platform dependency (C18), and unseen labour (C20), and are anchored in values like Sustainability (V21), Sovereignty (V22), and Responsibility and Care (V20).

This comprehensive framework articulates a stakeholder-led vision for generative AI in cultural and creative sectors—one that supports co-creation, fosters inclusion, and embeds responsibility into every layer of system design and deployment. Together, these design requirements form the basis for the HAMLET architecture and downstream prototyping activities. For detailed list of stakeholder requirements look chapter 4.6.3 and Table 10.

4.2 List of All Stakeholder Concerns, Values & Requirements

This chapter provides the list of all identified concerns, values and design requirements collected through chapters from 4.3 to 4.6.

4.2.1 Concerns

- **Authorship, Ownership, and Consent:** Many stakeholders voiced strong fears about plagiarism, copyright theft, and appropriation of creative labour. They stressed that AI systems must respect intellectual property, data provenance, and the consent of creators. Without safeguards, artists risk losing control over their work and cultural contributions being exploited without recognition.
- **Creativity, Authenticity, and Cultural Depth:** A recurring concern is that AI-generated outputs may lack authenticity, emotional resonance, or the “soul” of human creativity. Stakeholders fear homogenization, overproduction of generic content, and the erosion of artistic nuance, narrative richness, and embodied practices. For many, preserving cultural specificity and non-uniform creative expression is critical.
- **Bias, Exclusion, and Inequality:** Stakeholders highlighted risks of bias, racism, and systemic exclusion in AI tools, particularly of non-technical creatives and minority communities. There are worries about centralisation of power in big tech platforms, the reinforcement of social inequalities, and the danger of manipulation or misuse (e.g., propaganda, harmful ideologies). These issues demand transparency, fairness, and inclusivity in design.

- **Labour, Productivity, and Human Roles:** Instead of reducing workload, AI may increase pressure to produce more content at higher speeds, often at the expense of meaning and value. Stakeholders fear replacement of human creativity and labour, including staff reductions in cultural institutions. They emphasise that AI should complement rather than replace human roles.
- **Environmental and Infrastructural Impact:** Several stakeholders raised concerns about the ecological footprint of AI, particularly its high energy consumption and reliance on unsustainable infrastructures. This cluster stresses the need for sustainable, responsible AI development that considers both environmental costs and long-term resilience.

Table 5: General stakeholder's concerns about AI in CCI.

ID	Concern name	Description
C01	Lack of Consent & Opt-Out Options	Creators' work or data being used in training without permission or means of refusal.
C02	IP / Copyright Theft	Unlawful or unethical reproduction of artists' works without acknowledgment or compensation.
C03	Displacement by Automation	Anxiety that AI substitutes human labour and artistry rather than augmenting it.
C04	Loss of Creative Control	Risk that automation reduces artists to passive operators, stripping them of decision-making power.
C05	Loss of Artistic Identity	Fear that distinctive personal or cultural voices are blurred into algorithmically averaged aesthetics.
C06	Bias in Datasets and Models	Recognition that embedded social and cultural prejudices are reproduced in AI outcomes.
C07	Exclusion of Minorities	Systemic biases preventing fair representation or participation of marginalized groups.
C08	Erasure of Non-Dominant Worldviews	Neglect of indigenous, queer, or localized perspectives in training and outputs.
C09	Marginalization of Queer and Disabled Creatives	Underrepresentation or misrepresentation in data, tools, and cultural outputs.
C10	Cultural Flattening / Homogenization	Risk that dominant cultural frameworks overshadow minority or alternative worldviews.
C11	Manipulation through AI Outputs	Fear that outputs can be biased, misleading, or used to influence audiences deceptively.
C12	Over-Trust in Objectivity	Belief that AI systems produce neutral or "truthful" outputs, ignoring embedded biases.
C13	Ethics Treated as Afterthought	Concern that ethical issues are retrofitted rather than integral to design.
C14	Overproduction of Generic or "Soulless" Work	Concern that AI may flood cultural spaces with formulaic, homogenized content.
C15	Plagiarism	Outputs replicating existing works too closely, undermining originality.
C16	Unresolved Data Ownership	Lack of clarity over who controls training datasets, contributions, and derived content.
C17	Dependence on Centralized Platforms	Lock-in to corporate infrastructures that limit sovereignty and user control.
C18	Misaligned Vocabularies Between Disciplines	Difficulty of collaboration due to differing professional languages and timelines.
C19	Environmental Unsustainability	High energy costs and resource demands of large-scale AI models.

C20	Invisible or Undervalued Dataset Creation Labour	Workers' contributions in labelling, curation, and maintenance are hidden or exploited.
C21	Opacity of Systems (Black-Box AI)	Hidden processes that make it impossible for artists or audiences to understand how outcomes are produced.
C22	Shallow or Flattened Emotional Expression	Outputs lacking the depth of affect, narrative resonance, or moral complexity found in human creation.
C23	Over-Standardization / Loss of Surprise	Rigid workflows and predictable outputs undermining experimentation and improvisation.
C24	Lack of Interoperability in Workflows	Tools failing to integrate with existing production pipelines, hindering usability.
C25	Losing Lived Experience	Risk of reducing physical presence to data, losing the lived body in abstraction.
C26	Homogenization & Mediocrity	Risk of mainstreaming creativity and flooding the market with mediocre AI content.
C27	Exclusion Risks	Lack of inclusivity and representation in AI design may alienate certain communities and reinforce inequalities.

4.2.2 Values

- **Creativity, Authorship, and Authenticity:** Stakeholders strongly value preserving the unique voice, authorship, and creative autonomy of human practitioners. AI is expected to assist rather than replace, supporting originality and authenticity in artistic expression. This cluster highlights the importance of safeguarding artistic identity while enabling human-AI collaboration.
- **Openness, Trust, and Transparency:** Values such as openness, critical thinking, and trust were emphasized to counter opaque AI systems. Transparency in how tools function, what data they use, and how outputs are generated is seen as essential for accountability and meaningful use.
- **Fairness, Respect, and Ownership:** Stakeholders demand fairness in how AI engages with creative work, including respect for intellectual property, data provenance, and consent. Ownership is a foundational value, ensuring that creators maintain control over their contributions and are not exploited by automated systems.
- **Diversity, Inclusivity, and Cultural Respect:** A strong emphasis was placed on inclusivity and the respect for cultural specificity. AI systems should reflect diverse perspectives, avoid homogenization, and enable participation by non-technical users. This value cluster stresses democratic access and cultural sensitivity.
- **Depth, Embodiment, and Situated Creativity:** Values of emotional expression, narrative depth, and embodied knowledge underline the need for AI to support-not flatten-complex, situated practices such as live performance, somatic knowledge, or culturally embedded creativity.
- **Sustainability, Responsibility, and Care:** Stakeholders also voiced ecological and ethical values, stressing that AI must be designed with environmental responsibility in mind. Care-driven approaches emphasize sustainable infrastructures and long-term accountability in both development and use.
- **Playfulness, Experimentation, and Freedom:** Finally, stakeholders value experimentation, open-ended exploration, and creative agency. AI systems should foster play, improvisation, and “happy accidents,” rather than reinforcing standardization, speed, or productivity pressures.

Table 6: General stakeholder's values underlying AI in CCI.

ID	Value Name	Description
V01	Creativity, Authorship, Authenticity	Upholding the originality and integrity of artistic expression, ensuring that AI enhances rather than dilutes or imitates creative identity.
V02	Creative Autonomy	Safeguarding the artist's ability to steer and shape processes without undue automation or machine-driven outcomes.
V03	Artistic Authenticity	Ensuring that creative outputs preserve the personal, cultural, or aesthetic intentions of the author.
V04	Meaningful Collaboration	Viewing AI as a co-creative partner that supports rather than replaces the human creative role.
V05	Freedom	Guaranteeing artists flexibility in workflows, interpretations, and the capacity to reject or modify AI-generated results.
V06	Ownership	Recognizing and protecting intellectual property, data contributions, and authorship.
V07	Accessibility	Lowering technical barriers so that non-specialists and marginalized groups can participate.
V08	Adaptability	Ensuring AI tools can be tailored to diverse creative contexts, disciplines, and evolving artistic practices.
V09	Playfulness	Embracing experimentation, improvisation, and serendipity in creative processes.
V10	Emotional Depth	Recognizing affective, moral, and narrative qualities as central to artistic value.
V11	Openness, Trust, Transparency	Making processes, data, and infrastructures visible and comprehensible to foster trust and accountability.
V12	Fairness	Treating all contributors-creators, users, data providers-equitably, with attention to power imbalances.
V13	Respect	Acknowledging cultural traditions, personal rights, and community knowledge in AI-supported processes.
V14	Inclusivity	Opening participation to underrepresented groups, enabling diverse entry points into AI-supported creativity.
V15	Diversity	Supporting multiple cultural frameworks, perspectives, and creative expressions rather than privileging one norm.
V16	Cultural Respect, Sensitivity & Specificity	Embedding awareness of cultural heritage, non-Western knowledge, and localized practices into AI tools.
V17	Situated Knowledge	Valuing embodied, contextual, and tacit knowledge as integral to creative and technical work.
V18	Ethical AI Use	Designing and deploying systems in ways that respect human dignity, societal values, and professional norms.
V19	Reflectivity and Critical Thinking	Encouraging users to interrogate the assumptions and limitations of AI, fostering awareness of biases and systemic conditions.
V20	Responsibility and Care	Ensuring that design and deployment consider long-term cultural, social, and ecological impacts.
V21	Sustainability	Designing systems mindful of ecological costs, resource use, and planetary impact.
V22	Sovereignty	Advocating decentralization and community control over infrastructures, data, and creative ecosystems.

4.2.3 Design requirements

How can concerns and values be translated into operational context of GAI? What are the processes and roles supporting implementation of these translations?

How can concerns and values of newly developed GAI technologies and tools be tested and validated?

Table 7: All stakeholder requirements based on all the previous chapters.

ID	Design Requirement	Description	Concerns	Values
Human-Centred Creativity & Control				
DR01	Human-Centred Creativity	AI systems should enhance exploration and assist with repetitive or technical tasks, but never substitute human creativity or embodied artistic practice.	C01, C02	V01, V02, V04, V05
DR02	Human-in-the-Loop Creative Control	Tools must provide real-time human oversight and control, enabling creators to shape, override, or refine outputs at every stage.	C01	V02, V04, V13
DR03	Alignment with Artistic Intentions	AI outputs must adapt to and respect artistic structures-such as rhythm, dramaturgy, narrative flow, symbolism, and temporal dynamics.	C04	V03, V04, V05, V20
DR04	Allow Prompt Negotiation and Iterative Exploration	Systems should support dynamic, back-and-forth interaction with prompts, enabling creators to explore evolving ideas and refine direction iteratively.	C15, C21	V04, V07, V19
DR05	Enable Feedback Loops and Live Responsiveness	Tools must respond immediately to user input or environmental data, allowing continuous interaction in creative or performative settings.	C21	V04, V19
DR06	Balance of Control & Emergence	AI systems should combine user-defined constraints with room for serendipitous, unexpected, or generative output to support discovery.	C01, C15, C21	V01, V04, V19
DR07	Enable Iterative, Time-Based & Performative Use	AI should support evolving use over time, allowing integration into live performances, rehearsals, or long-term creative development.		V01, V02
DR08	Interactive Storytelling Support	Design AI tools to support modular, branching narratives with rich input/output conditions-empowering creators to curate and remix stories flexibly.	C03	V01, V09
DR09	Support Playfulness & Improvisation	Interactions with AI should invite open-ended experimentation, playful deviation, and rule-breaking as core aspects of the creative process.	C21	V04, V19
DR10	Embrace Randomness & Generativity	Systems should allow controlled randomness and variation, reflecting the unpredictable, emergent nature of generative processes.	C21	V04, V05, V19
DR11	Foster Speculative & Critical Imagination	AI must support not only efficiency but also imaginative exploration-enabling creators to envision alternative worlds, systems, or futures.	C14, C16	V07, V15
DR12	Taking Care of Meaning & Trust	Generated content must maintain reliability and preserve meaning, ensuring audiences can place trust in the creative and cultural value of the work.	C10, C24	V04, V13, V20
DR13	Persistence	Tools must ensure continuity across software updates and environments, preventing workflow disruptions and preserving creative investment.	C23	V09
Transparency, Explainability & Literacy				

DR14	Transparent, Interpretable Outputs	AI-generated content must be understandable to users, prioritising clarity, traceability, and coherence over mere efficiency.	C21	V11, V19
DR15	Explainability	Systems should provide insight into their generative logic, allowing users to review, guide, and modify decision processes step-by-step.	C21	V11, V19
DR16	Make Rule Systems & Logic Transparent	AI systems must expose their underlying algorithms, constraints, and decision-making logic to foster understanding and trust.	C21	V11, V19
DR17	Transparency	Clearly communicate how data is sourced, processed, and used in AI generation, including biases, limitations, and transformations.	C21	V11
DR18	Reveal System Infrastructure & Power Relations	Tools should disclose the infrastructural and labour systems behind AI-including environmental, political, and economic impacts.	C20	V20, V22
DR19	Bias & Feedback Loops	Prevent AI from reusing and retraining its own outputs in ways that reinforce dominant stereotypes, amateur bias, or creative stagnation.	C06	V15, V19
DR20	AI Literacy & Education	AI systems should be designed to help users build critical literacy-learning to question, interpret, and reflect on outputs rather than over-trust them.	C11	V18, V19
Access, Collaboration & Interdisciplinarity				
DR21	Democratize Access & Reduce Technical Barriers	Interfaces must be usable by artists with varying levels of technical expertise, without requiring coding or AI-specific training.	C07, C27	V07, V14
DR22	Accessibility & Mutability	Tools should accommodate disabled users and allow flexible representation of the body-supporting queer, neurodivergent, and non-normative experiences.	C09	V07, V14
DR23	Artist-Technologist Collaboration	Tools intended for creative use must be co-designed with artists through participatory, domain-specific processes.	C18, C26	V04, V19
DR24	Bridge Disciplines through Mediation & Translation	Incorporate mediators or translators who can align artistic and technical vocabularies, workflows, and timelines during development.	C18, C26	V04, V19
DR25	Consider Open-Prototyping	Adopt iterative, open, and transparent prototyping cycles that invite stakeholder feedback and critique at all stages.		V04, V11
Embodiment, Performance & Sensory Interaction				
DR26	Support Embodied and Sensory Interaction	Allow AI to engage with bio-signals, gestures, and environmental stimuli, enabling physical and experiential interaction.	C25	V03, V17
DR27	Enable Situated, Embodied, and Contingent Interaction	Systems must adapt to real-time, affective, and spatial conditions-responding to the nuance of live or site-specific creative contexts.	C25	V03, V17
DR28	Embodied Dialogue	AI must be capable of reading, analysing, and generating movement, acting as a responsive co-creator in multimodal or choreographic practices.	C25	V03, V17
Cultural Context, Diversity & Ethical Design				

DR29	Embed Cultural Context & Non-Western Frameworks	AI must accommodate diverse epistemologies, aesthetics, and traditions-going beyond dominant Western norms.	C14, C16	V15, V16
DR30	Expose and Address Cultural Biases	Make cultural assumptions and training data visible, allowing users to challenge or redirect them.	C13, C14, C16	V15, V19
DR31	Challenge Normativity & Queer the Dataset	Use AI to question fixed categories and introduce diverse, non-normative identities and aesthetics into generative output.	C14, C17	V14, V15
DR32	Non-Mainstream Outputs	Systems should produce content that reflects marginal, local, or underrepresented cultural forms-not just mainstream defaults.	C14, C04	V15, V01
DR33	Foster Multi-Perspective Meaning-Making	Design for layered interpretation, allowing audiences and performers to co-construct meaning in situated and plural ways.	C14, C10, C26	V15, V20
DR34	Recognize & Express Moral and Emotional Values	Treat emotions and moral insights as valid inputs and outputs of AI systems-reflecting ethical complexity.	C10, C24	V10, V20
DR35	Support Critical and Ethical Reflectivity	Expose training biases, embedded assumptions, and the normative implications of AI systems to support reflective design and use.	C11, C12	V19, V18
Consent, Data Governance & Infrastructure Autonomy				
DR36	Data Governance & Consent	Ensure transparent policies for how creative data is used, stored, and shared-always respecting the creator's intent.	C06, C08, C09	V12, V20
DR37	Support Consent & Voice Ownership	Let artists define the terms of use for their synthetic likenesses or biometric representations.	C06, C07, C08	V01, V12
DR38	Build Conditions for Consent & Opt-Out Mechanisms	Allow creators to withdraw participation and data at any time without penalty or residual exploitation.	C06	V12, V22
DR39	Decentralize Infrastructure	Prioritise locally hosted, transparent systems that avoid reliance on centralised cloud platforms or Big Tech APIs.	C18	V22, V11
DR40	Foster Data Sovereignty	Design systems that support offline operation, local control, and artist-driven governance over data use.	C09, C18	V22, V20
DR41	Dependency on Platforms	Avoid subscription-based or locked-in ecosystems that reduce user autonomy and control.	C18	V22
DR42	Protected Creative Environment	Ensure that creative inputs are secure, not exploited for training purposes, and protected from unauthorised reuse.	C07, C08, C09	V12, V20
DR43	Consider Environmental Footprint	As AI is in energy very consuming technology, consider energy footprint of development and use of the system.	C19	V21
Technical Interoperability & Workflow Integration				
DR44	Technical Interoperability	Support standard file formats and protocols across creative tools (e.g., MIDI, MusicXML, WAV, Blender, Unity, etc.).	C23, C22	V11, V08

DR45	Model AI as Public, Participatory Infrastructure	Frame AI tools as civic infrastructure-shared, discussable, and oriented toward cultural participation and public value.	C05, C12	V06, V20
------	--	--	----------	----------

4.3 From the Pioneers to the Contemporaries of AI in CCI

Artists have long played a foundational role in shaping how we understand and engage with artificial intelligence. Long before AI entered mainstream discourse, artists were already working with machines and computation to rethink authorship, aesthetics, and systems of meaning making.

The first major step toward conceiving of a more relational interaction with machines, no longer seen as rigid tools but as entities capable of generating feedback, came with the birth of cybernetics in the 1940s. Up until then dominant perception saw machines as simple, rigid tools, either for performing physical labour or as repositories of stored knowledge.⁷ Cybernetics, however, introduced a **new paradigm: machines could be imagined, and increasingly designed, as systems capable of receiving, processing, and returning information**. Norbert Wiener, who coined the term, described cybernetics as a science of communication and control of that relied on feedback loops to make systems self-regulating. This shift carried profound implications not only for engineering but also for the arts and social sciences. Anthropologist Margaret Mead, for instance, described cybernetics as “a form of cross-disciplinary thought which made it possible for members of many disciplines to communicate with each other easily in a language which all could understand.” In this sense, cybernetics was inherently transdisciplinary, reconstructing the logic of living organisms in computational terms and opening a new space for artists, scientists, and thinkers to explore the mutual shaping of humans and machines.

Many early cyberneticists originated from the field mathematics and mechanics. They often began by exploring technical abilities of a machine later diving deeper into experimental expressions of computation that could be seen as more artistic or even philosophical rather than aiming to simply showcasing the extent of their technical capabilities.⁸ In their experiments the relationship with the machine sometimes assumed an active participation or a form of a dialogue between the human operator and the machine.

A great example of treating **machines as creative collaborators** can be found in one of the early cybernetics works by Gordon Pask called *Musicolour*.⁹ This 1953 piece was a mechanical and electronic machine operating with sound input via microphone capable of analysing it for frequency, attack and rhythm. Following the input, the machine would produce various light patterns triggered by its servo motors. *Musicolour* would only respond if given input by the human operator. Moreover, it was also capable of adjusting the output if it detected that the input became repetitive, or in other words it was designed to get “bored” and stop reacting stimulating new action from the operator. This would also signal to the operator of the *Musicolour* that to achieve desired outcome they have to work actively with the machine.¹⁰ Pask wrote, “the machine is designed to entrain the performer and to couple [them] into the system”. Performers also felt they could train the machine to produce the sorts of patterns they preferred.¹⁰

⁷ Link : Thomas Dreher - History of Computer Art https://iasl.uni-muenchen.de/links/GCA_book.pdf#page=398.11

⁸ Link Amy Goodchild <https://www.amygoodchild.com/blog/computer-art-50s-and-60s>

⁹ Link: Gordon Pask - Musicolor <https://rhythmiclight.com/timeline/gordon-pasks-musicolour-machine/>

¹⁰ Link: Gordon Pask - A comment, a case history and a plan <https://pangaro.com/pask/Pask%20Cybernetic%20Serendipity%20Musicolour%20and%20Colloquy%20of%20Mobiles.pdf>

Figure 2: a) Gordon Pask, *Musicolor* (1953), b) Nicolas Schöffer, *CYSP -1* (1956), c) Martin Graetz, Wayne Wiitanen, Bob Saunders, Steve Piner, *Spacewar!* (1962), d) (1956), Vera Molnár, *Interruptions* (1968), e) Jeanne Beaman and Paul le Vasseur, *Random Dances* (1968), f) Harold Cohen *AARON* (1972-2010), g) Karl Sims, *Evolved Virtual Creatures* (1994), h) Anna Ridler, *Mosaic Virus* (2018), i) Fig. 9: Kate Crawford and Vladan Joler, *Anatomy of an AI System* (2018).

Around that time broader range of artists became increasingly more interested in capabilities of machine interaction. Artists began to see computation as a **medium of participation, improvisation, and generative exploration**. They were often particularly fascinated by the emergent notion of “electronic brain” and what kind of output it could autonomously produce. In 1956 Nicolas Schöffer premiered *CYSP-1* (a name composed of the first letters of *CY*bernetics and *SP*atiodynamic). His sculptures’ “reactions” were governed by computers programmed with feedback loops, allowing the work to self-regulate in response to environmental changes. Photo-electric cells and a microphone built into the sculpture sampled the variations of colour and light and sound intensity and made it interactive.

At the same time, experiments with early computer games began to influence artistic thinking. *Spacewar!* (1962),¹¹ developed at MIT by Martin Graetz, Wayne Wiitanen, Bob Saunders, Steve Piner, was not conceived as an artwork, yet it embodied cybernetic principles: **continuous feedback between player input and machine response, and the framing of the computer as an interactive environment rather than a static tool.** Early digital art groups such as the Computer Technique Group in Japan or Charles Csuri's computer animations borrowed from the game's underlying idea-that human and machine could enter into a loop of co-creation. What started as playful experimentation on research lab computers thus fed directly into artistic practice with feedback, and user interaction became defining features of computer-based art.

In the same decade the lines between the object and subject of an art piece began to blur as artists started to embrace another aspect of machine generated outputs - the randomness.

Pioneers such as Georg Nees, Frieder Nake, and Vera Molnár began using plotters and rule-based programming to create artworks. Molnár, who famously developed her "machine imaginaire" before gaining access to real computers, later reflected: "Instead of starting from 'I am a genius...' I come up with a system. It's an experimental method, taken step by step."¹² Her work *Interruptions* (1968) used controlled randomness to explore the tension between order and variation that challenged traditional notions of authorship and control.

In 1968, *Random Dance*-a performance created by dancer Jeanne Beaman in collaboration with computer scientist Paul le Vasseur-attracted attention precisely because dance was considered one of the least likely art forms to be computerized.¹³ Beaman developed three lists of instructions-tempo, movement, and direction-from which the computer randomly generated sequences for groups of one to nine dancers. The procedure was relatively simple, yet **the results remained unpredictable: the same computer-generated score could yield radically different performances depending on the dancers' interpretations.** By incorporating generative methods into choreography, Beaman's experiment marked an early and unconventional application of cybernetic principles within the performing arts.

As AI research accelerated in the 1960s and 1970s, neural networks and computer-aided design (CAD) tools opened new horizons for artistic experimentation. Harold Cohen's *AARON* (1972-2010)-one of the first genuine AI art systems-showed that **machines could be programmed with stylistic and spatial knowledge to autonomously produce drawings.** Cohen unsettled conventional ideas of authorship by asking: "If AARON makes the drawing, who is the artist?"¹⁴

By the 1990s, artists such as Karl Sims extended these explorations through evolutionary algorithms. Works like *Primordial Dance* (1991) and *Evolved Virtual Creatures* (1994) modelled mutation and natural selection, **shifting the focus from static outputs to dynamic, evolving systems capable of generating unforeseen forms.**

Especially through 20th century, artists have been oriented toward the future, assessing the present state of their work and anticipating what might become achievable next. Today's generative AI artists inherit this

¹¹ Link Spacewar! <https://www.computerhistory.org/pdp-1/spacewar/>

¹² Link: RightClickSave Interview with Vera Molnár, 2022: <https://www.rightclicksave.com/article/an-interview-with-vera-molnar>

¹³ Link: Jeanne Beaman, Paul le Vasseur - Random Dances <https://museum.dataart.com/short-stories/random-dances-in-cybernetic-serendipity>

¹⁴ Link: Harold Cohen - AARON: <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/AARON>

lineage but work in a vastly different context: one defined by commercial platforms, deep learning models, and global concerns over ethics, labour, and representation. In contrast to early cybernetic works much of today computation is obscured by complicated systems and hardware that artists might find challenging to engage with. **That problem in on itself becomes an object of artistic inquiry.** Anna Ridler, for instance, hand-curated datasets to interrogate the “black box” of machine learning. Her project *Mosaic Virus* (2018) trained GANs on her own tulip drawings, linking economic speculation with algorithmic instability. “A dataset is creative work,” she insists, “and becomes an artwork in and of itself.”¹⁵

Other artists seem to echo early enthusiasm of cyberneticists emphasising collaboration affordances of AI over automation. In her *Drawing Operations* series, Sougwen Chung trains robotic arms on her own gestures to perform real-time co-creation, stating: “Making with machines is not just about automation. It’s about listening, improvising, becoming with the system.”¹⁶

Still others dive deeper into **critical takes on AI into through performative and political lens.** Jake Elwes’s *Zizi - Queering the Dataset* (2019) subverts facial recognition systems by training GANs on drag performers, exposing gender bias in training data. Meanwhile, Kate Crawford and Vladan Joler’s *Anatomy of an AI System* (2018) maps the ecological and human cost of a single smart speaker, revealing how AI systems are embedded in extractive global infrastructures. As Crawford writes: “It’s not just about data-it’s about minerals, labour, power, and inequality.”¹⁷

Across these diverse practices, artists have not only contributed to the aesthetic evolution of AI but have helped shape public understanding of its risks and possibilities. Their work reminds us that AI is not merely technical-it is social, speculative, and deeply human.

WAAG identified more than 30 international artists from more than 50-years of history of AI in art. This selection provides historical foundation to forming of Design Requirements:

Table 8: Design requirements based on the literacy review of global pioneer and contemporary AI in CCI.

Design Requirement	Description	Artwork Reference
Prioritize Human-Machine Co-Creation over Automation	Design AI systems to amplify human creativity and intuition rather than replace it, supporting collaborative creation.	Sougwen Chung, <i>Drawing Operations</i> Unit; Harold Cohen, AARON
Enable Iterative, Time-Based, and Performative Use	Allow for live, evolving, or performance-based interaction with generative systems.	Annie Dorsen, <i>Prometheus Firebringer</i> ; David Rokeby, <i>Very Nervous System</i>
Make Rule Systems and Logic Transparent	Expose the algorithmic rules, decision paths, and underlying logic of generative systems.	Manfred Mohr, P-511/D; Harold Cohen, AARON
Make Dataset Creation Visible and valued	Acknowledge and document the human labour in curating and labelling training datasets.	Anna Ridler, <i>Mosaic Virus</i> ; Stephanie Dinkins, <i>Not the Only One</i>

¹⁵ Link: Anna Ridler – *Mosaic Virus*: <https://joinreboot.org/p/artist-datasets>

¹⁶ Link: Sougwen Chung – *Drawing Operations*: <https://www.sougwen.com/projects/drawing-operations>

¹⁷ Link: Kate Crawford & Vladan Joler – *Anatomy of an AI System*: <https://anatomyof.ai/>

Support Embodied and Sensory Interaction	Incorporate bodily gestures, bio-signals, and environmental inputs to enable physical engagement.	Sougwen Chung, Drawing Operations; Seiko Mikami, Desire of Codes
Enable Feedback Loops and Live Responsiveness	Design systems that respond in real time to user input or environmental changes.	Ernest Edmonds, Fragment; Bulat Galeev, Prometheus Institute Works
Embed Cultural Context and Non-Western Frameworks	Incorporate diverse epistemologies and aesthetics into system training and behaviour.	Bulat Galeev, Musico-Chromo-Logo Schema; Yoichiro Kawaguchi, Growth Model
Queer the Dataset and Challenge Normativity	Use AI to subvert gender norms and introduce diverse identities into generative outputs.	Jake Elwes, Zizi - Queering the Dataset
Support Consent and Voice Ownership	Ensure artists maintain control and agency over their synthetic representations.	Holly Herndon, Holly+
Reveal System Infrastructure and Power Relations	Expose the hidden layers of data extraction, labour, and environmental cost within AI systems.	Kate Crawford & Vladan Joler, Anatomy of an AI System
Foster Speculative and Critical Imagination	Use generative AI to imagine alternative realities, speculative futures, and systemic critiques.	Memo Akten, Deep Meditations; Tega Brain, Unfit Bits
Embrace Randomness and Generativity	Provide ways to incorporate unpredictability and variation, showcasing reality of working with generative machines.	Vera Molnár, <i>Interruptions</i> ; Georg Nees; Frieder Nake
Support Playfulness and Improvisation	In relation to previously mentioned challenging of normativity, treat interactions with AI as a space of exploration experimentation and play.	MIT Spacewar; Charles Csur, Hummingbird animations; Evolved Virtual Creatures

For more details, see D1.1 Annex#1: From the Pioneers to the Contemporaries of AI in CCI.

4.4 Interviews with Experts

This chapter synthesizes insights gathered through expert interviews conducted for HAMLET D1.1, focusing on how GAI systems can better serve artistic, ethical, and collaborative practices within the cultural and creative sectors. The interviews with artists, technologists, game studios, and scholars reveal a set of shared concerns and aspirations that should guide the design of generative AI tools in creative fields such as games, theatre, and dance.

A central theme across the conversations is that **AI should act as a collaborator, not a replacement**. For game designer and educator **Sam Liberty**, AI can be a powerful technical enabler, lowering barriers for non-programmers and accelerating workflows, but it must not undermine artistic quality or be used solely to produce “good enough” content at scale. Game developer and AI researcher **Lazaros Vrysis** expresses that even though AI-assisted contents in games are gaining certain acceptance, there should be human always involved in the loop, also for the quality control. Similarly, Martin Eglseder, AI Cultivator of **CipSoft**, the independent developer and operator of online games, emphasized that AI should **remove chores and free up time for creativity**, not reduce jobs-highlighting a company-wide principle of human authorship and accountability.

In theatre and dance, **embodiment** becomes the crucial requirement. Prof. **Kristina Höök**, professor in Interaction Design, argues that AI tools can be conceived beyond disembodied text or image generation and engage directly with the **lived body through wearables, haptics, or responsive garments**. For her, intelligence is inseparable from embodiment, and AI should enrich rather than flatten aesthetic experience. Mime artist and interactive performance artist **Niek Vanoosterweyck** echoes this, treating the theatre space and its technological systems as **co-creators in feedback loops** that provoke movement discovery. He stresses valuing glitches, seams, and boundaries as creative opportunities, rather than aiming for seamless automation.

Performance artist **Elioa Steffen**, heavily influenced by queer art lineages, adds further layers of concern around **representation, consent, and cultural sensitivity**. She warns against “neutral” or default body models, which erase diversity and reinforce normativity. This is echoed by Dr. **Phaedra Shanbaum**, assistant professor in media studies, as she considers that AI tools should avoid reinforcing normative binaries and instead **enable diverse, non-normative bodies and aesthetics**. For **Steffen**, AI systems need to allow **mutable bodies**-recognizing queer embodiment, disability, and diverse identities. Theorist, artist, and educator **Flavia Dzodan** considers that **consent and agency** are also crucial: performers must retain control over their data and the option to remove themselves from datasets if they leave a project or company.

Beyond technical design, interviewees emphasise **ethical and infrastructural safeguards**. **Flavia Dzodan** highlights the need for frameworks that allow artists to **opt out of data appropriation** and considers artistic intervention open **public discussions of AI’s cultural biases**. **Abdelhadi Baaddi**, Head of Creative Technology of innovation:lab, similarly called for **local and offline models**, mediated collaborations between technologists and artists, and transparent acknowledgment of biases. Dr. **Matjaz Vidmar**, Deputy Director of the New Real, an international initiative integrating Humanities into the core of AI development, proposes **fair compensation, ownership, and consent mechanisms**, alongside lightweight, locally hosted models to reduce dependency on big tech. **Vidmar** recommends **Open Prototyping**¹⁸: iterative, collaborative, and transparent design process that comprises of six stages: scoping → connecting → play/prototyping → displaying → interpreting. He also suggests that **artists retain full ownership** of their data, models, and derivative works created with the help of AI platforms. Prof. **Maike Bleeker**, the principal investigator of research project Dramaturgy for Devices, stresses that artists must be involved early in development, to shape algorithmic behaviors and prevent the replication of problematic stereotypes.

Ethics, for Prof. **Sabine Roeser**, professor of ethics, is not a checklist but a practice of **emotional and contextual deliberation**. She urges that AI design must engage with moral emotions, embedding responsibility and human values into decision-making. Meanwhile, **Marlon Barrios Solano**, interdisciplinary artist, creative technologist, and researcher considers that we need to have epistemic awareness of the three interconnected forces beneath techno-solutionism and digital utopianism that creates the fever of AI: patriarchy, colonialism, and capitalism: be critical and reflective about **the underlying assumptions** when an AI tool is being conceived. Dr. **Phaedra Shanbaum** stresses that data collection is never neutral, and one needs to ask who is the data about? where does it come from? why is it collected? who has access and input? Both Dr. **Matjaz Vidmar** and **Elioa Steffen** express that when designing AI tools, technologists need to take **environmental responsibilities** into consideration.

¹⁸ Open Prototyping <https://www.newreal.cc/openprototyping> Last access 19th Sept 2025

Flavia Dzodan cautions the **unethical aspect of AI’s algorithmic processes that produce a frictionless experience by manipulating feelings and emotions**, as these processes can lead to dependency and addiction, like those AI platforms created by Big Tech. Dr. **Vanessa Hanneschläger**, Head of European Collaboration of FESTIVAL/PRIX Ars Electronica emphasizes: to resist big tech centralization, tools must be **open and open-source, collaborative, and extendable**-but allow individual creators to retain autonomy, and **artists and communities must have a voice in shaping AI tools and datasets**, not just consuming outputs.

Based on the interviews, it is clear that **technologists should collaborate with artists through open, iterative, and ethically grounded processes** that recognize artists not merely as end-users but as **co-creators of AI tools**. Artists bring embodied knowledge, cultural sensitivity, and aesthetic priorities that cannot be anticipated by purely technical design. As Dr. **Matjaž Vidmar** and Prof. **Maike Bleeker** emphasized, artists need to be involved from the earliest stages to shape how algorithms behave and to ensure systems remain meaningful for creative exploration. Collaboration should also respect **consent, ownership, and fair compensation**, as highlighted by **Eiloe Steffen**, ensuring that artists retain agency over their data, bodies, and cultural practices. Such partnerships require a spirit of **dialogue and mutual learning**, sometimes mediated by a tech translator, as the artist and the technologist need to understand each other’s language, temporalities, processes, and implications of their decisions, with the goal to **strike a balance between artistic possibility and technical feasibility**, as **Abdelhadi Baaddi** suggested. where glitches, constraints, and frictions of an AI tool are seen not as failures but as opportunities for new creative vocabularies, echoing **Niek Vanoosterweyck’s** call to embrace seams and errors. In short, technologists should work with artists as **equal partners in experimentation**, cultivating AI tools that support creativity, diversity, and responsibility rather than imposing prefabricated solutions.

Together, these interviews form a rich foundation for HAMLET’s design framework, offering concrete recommendations grounded in real-world artistic practice. The insights help shape general design requirements that prioritize co-creation, ethical responsibility, cultural sensitivity, and interdisciplinary collaboration-all essential to the future of generative AI in the cultural domain.

WAAG approached 20 of experts out of which 13 responded for one-hour interviews. Selected experts were: researcher/creative; dancer/choreographer, performance artist, technologist & game developer; game design studio, theatre, dance and performance studies scholar; philosopher & ethicist; creative technologist; AI researcher. This selection provides practice-based foundation to forming of Design Requirements.

Table 9: Design requirements based on interviews with experts.

Design Requirement	Description	Related values	Concerns
Ensure Human-in-the-Loop Creative Control.	AI systems must support human oversight, allowing creators to shape, override, or adapt outputs in real time to retain agency and responsibility.	Responsibility and Care, Meaningful Collaboration.	Automation vs. Control - Delegating tasks to AI may compromise creative control or responsibility.
Artist-technologist collaboration	AI tools that are for creatives should be designed together with the creatives through co-creation	Meaningful Collaboration, Democratization of Tools.	Mainstream AI tools are often made by Big Tech and creatives are only users.
Support Critical and Ethical Reflexivity.	Tools should expose embedded values, training biases, and algorithmic assumptions, encouraging users to	Reflectivity and Critical Thinking, Transparency.	Over trust in system objectivity - Risk of users believing AI outputs are neutral

	reflect on system implications and ethics.		or 'true', leading to uncritical adoption.
Enable Situated, Embodied, and Continuous Interaction.	Systems must respond to bodily presence, affective cues, spatial contexts, and real-time events-embracing improvisation and environmental complexity.	Embodiment and Expressivity, Meaningful Collaboration.	Formalization vs. Intuition - Codifying creativity can undermine embodied or intuitive aspects of artistic work.
Make constraints transparent	AI systems should have infrastructural transparency so that creatives can use the constraints as creative inputs	Transparency and adaptability.	The dependency on API provided by Big Tech as their platforms might be more powerful.
Foster Multi-Perspective Meaning-Making.	Design must accommodate layered interpretations from performers, audiences, and non-human agents-eschewing fixed or universal outputs.	Cultural Sensitivity, Meaningful Collaboration.	Universality vs. Cultural Specificity - Generalized AI models may ignore or flatten cultural contexts.
Democratize Access and Reduce Technical Barriers.	Interfaces should be inclusive for artists with varying digital literacies, avoiding coding requirements and ensuring creative accessibility.	Democratization of Tools.	Exclusion through technological literacy - Artists without coding skills may be left out of design and use.
Allow Prompt Negotiation and Iterative Exploration.	Enable dynamic adjustment of inputs and queries, supporting evolving intentions, collaborative play, and exploration through feedback loops.	Meaningful Collaboration, Reflectivity and Critical Thinking.	Playfulness vs. Predictability - AI may encourage exploration but also reproduce expected patterns.
Align with Dramaturgical and Artistic Intentions.	Outputs must respect the temporal, symbolic, and performative structures of artistic work-supporting rhythms, tension, space, and narrative flow.	Embodiment and Expressivity, Meaningful Collaboration.	Quantifiable Data Represents Experience - Systems rely on data inputs, often overlooking tacit or affective dimensions.
Recognize and Express Moral and Emotional Values.	Systems should treat emotions not as noise but as signals-integrating affect into evaluation, expression, and ethical engagement.	Embodiment and Expressivity, Responsibility and Care.	Emotional and value pluralism is often stripped out in system design.
Decentralize Infrastructure and Foster Data Sovereignty.	Avoid dependency on Big Tech APIs; design for offline, locally hosted, and transparent systems with artist consent over data usage.	Responsibility and Care, Transparency.	Cloud and platform infrastructures - Centralized systems concentrate control and surveillance capabilities.
Build Conditions for Consent and Opt-Out Mechanisms.	Provide frameworks for artists to decide whether and how their work is used, and the ability to withdraw consent at any point.	Responsibility and Care, Transparency.	Lack of opt-out framework for artists - Creators have little agency to control use of their data in AI systems.
Create Transparent, Interpretable Outputs.	Prioritize intelligibility and narrative transparency over efficiency or algorithmic 'correctness'-supporting trust and co-creation.	Transparency, Reflectivity and Critical Thinking.	Opacity vs. Trust - Black-box models reduce trust by hiding decision processes.
Bridge Disciplines through Mediation and Translation.	Incorporate roles like tech dramaturges or translators to align creative and technical processes, timelines, and vocabularies.	Meaningful Collaboration, Democratization of Tools.	Institutional mediation - Lack of roles that help align artistic and technical

			timelines and vocabularies.
Expose and Address Cultural Biases.	Make data biases and cultural assumptions visible to users and audiences; allow engagement, critique, and redirection in design.	Cultural Sensitivity, Reflectivity and Critical Thinking.	Reinforcing racialised biases that are embedded in societies. Marginalization of cultural difference - AI trained on dominant norms may erase or underrepresent minority worldviews.
Accessibility and Mutability	Consider making AI tools accessible to users with disabilities. Make the representation of the body mutable so that queer and disable users feel welcome.	Cultural Sensitivity, Reflectivity and Critical Thinking.	Marginalization of creatives with disabilities and queer creatives by AI platforms
Consider open-prototyping	Use iterative, collaborative, and transparent design process.	Meaningful Collaboration, Reflectivity and Critical Thinking.	Blackbox design process instead of iterative collaborative process.
Model AI as Public, Participatory Infrastructure.	Develop AI tools that act as shared, accessible, and discussable platforms for civic, artistic, and ethical co-creation-mirroring values of public space.	Democratization of Tools, Responsibility and Care.	Disempowerment of cultural actors in tech-heavy systems - Lack of citizen voice and access in AI-led design.

For more details, see D1.1. Annex#2: Design requirements from Interviews.

4.5 Workshops with Pilots and Enablers

WAAG organized three workshops with HAMLET Pilots and Enablers to map their use cases, creative and technical challenges, and underlying concerns. The aim was not only to gather insights from their practices and assess assumptions, expectations, and relevance, but also to create a space for shared reflection and collective discussion. As a result, the outcomes are not merely unilateral inputs, but already represent re-framed perspectives-emerging from dialogue between primary and secondary users on one side, and enabling stakeholders on the other.

Table 10: Design requirements based on the workshops with Pilots and Enablers.

Design requirement	Description	Related values	Concerns
Support Co-Creation Between Human and AI.	Enable collaborative workflows where artists can direct, steer, and modify AI-generated content meaningfully across domains.	Human-AI Collaboration, Creative Flexibility	Risk of creative displacement - AI could dominate rather than support human expression
Preserve Artistic Identity and Authorship.	Systems must retain the creator's unique style and expressive language, avoiding homogenized outputs.	Creative Autonomy, Artistic Authenticity	Loss of artistic identity; Generic AI output
Respect Artistic Autonomy and Critical Intent.	Design with space for refusal, ambiguity, and contradiction-allowing for	Creative Autonomy, Cultural Specificity	Automation vs. Empowerment

	dissenting or subversive creative choices.		
Ensure Creative Control and Editability.	Provide artists with intuitive tools for modifying and curating AI outputs at different stages of production.	Creative Autonomy, Transparency	Opacity of model behaviour; Risk of artists losing agency
Provide Transparent, Ethical AI Infrastructure.	Include information on datasets, model limitations, and ownership in ways that allow ethical reflection and accountability.	Transparency, Ethical AI Use	IP/legal uncertainties; Ethics as afterthought
Enable Iterative and Real-Time Creative Feedback Loops.	Allow dynamic, on-the-fly refinement during creation, rehearsal, or performance phases, supporting improvisation and flow.	Playfulness and Experimentation, Creative Flexibility	Overreliance on technology or creativity is restricted by technology
Accommodate Embodied and Somatic Knowledge.	Interfaces and models must respect the non-verbal, experiential intelligence of bodies-especially in choreography and performance.	Embodied Knowledge and Intuition	Data formalization vs. somatic nuance
Culturally-Aware Generation.	AI should reflect and respect diverse cultural expressions, vocabularies, and aesthetic traditions, rather than reproduce dominant defaults.	Cultural Specificity and Contextuality	Cultural homogenization
Foster Emotional and Narrative Depth.	Systems should not only be technically functional but also able to support storytelling, atmosphere, and emotional resonance.	Narrative and Emotional Expressivity	Loss of emotional nuance; Algorithmic generalisation and homogenisation vs. originality
Balance Real-Time and Pre-Composed Workflows.	Support both spontaneous live performance and carefully crafted pre-production use cases, and the transitions between them.	Creative Flexibility, Workflow Efficiency	Speed vs. reflective practice
Facilitate Access for Non-Technical Creatives.	Prioritize usability and onboarding for artists with little or no coding or AI training, avoiding technological gatekeeping.	Audience Inclusion and Accessibility	Non-technical creators at risk of exclusion
Support Cross-Disciplinary Workflows.	Systems need to accommodate diverse practices (e.g., narrative design in game design and theatre, music for game design and dance), enabling interoperability between them.	Human-AI Collaboration, Inclusivity	Platform constraints vs. creative diversity
Enable Hybrid and Phygital Performance Modes.	Systems should integrate seamlessly into both physical and digital environments, including XR and immersive spaces.	Hybrid Environments, Creative Autonomy	Technological inconsistency
Produce assets suitable for real production use in game design	Pipeline integration is key: the tool should offer APIs or portal access so generated assets can be iterated, controlled, and seamlessly integrated into our existing workflow.	Human-AI Collaboration, Creative Autonomy,	Text to image has challenges when it comes to style/consistency/ease-of use/ controllability by non-experts.

Harnessing evolutionary AI technology to drive storytelling in game design.	Procedurally generative system that creates scenarios for players to explore on the fly, powered by evolutionary AI	Human-AI Collaboration, Creative Flexibility	Technical framework and a large quantity of source material are needed
IP protection	The system should avoid infringing on others' IP and protecting the users' IP	Creative Autonomy	Not many existing frameworks to refer to.
Support idiosyncratic choreographic language analysis	The system should be able to support idiosyncratic choreographic language analysis that will encourage adoption from other dance companies.	Human-AI Collaboration, Creative Flexibility	The existing system mainly uses Laban Movement Analysis.
Enable new creative processes in dance and choreography	The system should propose new ways to create dance and choreography that are informed by the movement analysis and generation.	Human-AI Collaboration, Creative Autonomy	No Stylistic Control in Generation. Absence of Contextual Coherence. Phase and Temporal Structure Control is Lacking. Lack of Semantics
User-centric design and advanced segmentation for audience engagement	For the audience analytics and engagement tool, it should be developed through collaboration with cultural organisations, ensuring the tool addresses real-world needs and is intuitive/easy to use. Detailed insights incorporating socio-demographic and regional factors, enabling tailored audience engagement strategies.	Human-AI Collaboration, Creative Autonomy	Privacy and Ethics: Maintaining compliance with data protection laws and ethical standards in analysing audience information.
Predictive Analytics; Scalability and Adaptability	For the audience analytics and engagement tool, it should forecast audience trends, aiding in proactive decision-making. It should evolve with user feedback and changing cultural landscapes, ensuring long-term relevance and impact.	Human-AI Collaboration, Creative Flexibility	Scalability and Cost-Efficiency: Ensuring the predictive analytics tools can handle large volumes of data efficiently (environmentally and cost).
Encourage Play and Experimentation.	Tools should enable deviation, play, failure, and reconfiguration, inviting open-ended exploration rather than fixed outputs.	Playfulness and Experimentation	Algorithmic constraints; Over-standardization

For more details, see D1.1 Annex#3: Design requirements from Pilots and Enablers.

4.6 Survey and Workshop with Stakeholders

To understand stakeholder needs in generative AI for the cultural and creative industries (CCI), HAMLET employed a qualitative and value-sensitive inquiry approach through a co-designed questionnaire. The survey served not only as a data collection instrument but also as a reflexive tool to surface stakeholder concerns, values, and practices. Questionnaires were chosen for their ease of distribution across diverse regions and professions, their accessibility to non-technical respondents, and their ability to combine structured and open-ended inputs for both qualitative and quantitative analysis.

Plan:

- Developing a questionnaire
- Publishing a questionnaire
- Communicating through partner and stakeholder networks
- Collecting feedback data
- Validation of feedback through the workshop with stakeholders
- Qualitative and quantitative data analysis

The questionnaire was structured around the creative workflows of key HAMLET sectors-dance, theatre, gaming, and media art - and addressed concerns identified in prior interviews and workshops. It was divided into eight concise parts:

- **Part A: Demographics & Role** - To contextualize responses by profession, expertise, and geographic setting.
- **Part B: Creative Practices** - To map current tools, workflows, and the presence or absence of AI use.
- **Part C: Experience with AI** - To assess prior exposure to or experimentation with AI tools.
- **Part D: Needs** - Asking for concrete expectations, desires, and frustrations with use of GAI.
- **Part E: Concerns & reflections** - To collect doubts, critiques, or deeper concerns that stakeholders have about AI in CCI contexts.

The questionnaire was published on Waag's free & open source LimeSurvey platform and distributed via the HAMLET Community Hub, direct partner networks, and social media platforms to ensure broad reach across geographies and disciplines.

For detailed survey, see Annex #4: Stakeholder Requirements Survey & Workshop.

4.6.1 Analysis Methodology

The responses were analysed through a mixed-methods approach:

- **Quantitative Analysis:** Closed-form questions were processed statistically to identify trends and correlations across roles, sectors, and attitudes. Results were visualized through bar charts and cross-tabulations, serving as indicators for shared design needs.
- **Qualitative Analysis:** Open-ended responses were analysed using thematic analysis, informed by value-sensitive design and critical making principles. The analysis followed these steps:
 - **Familiarization** - Researchers read through all responses to understand their tone and content.
 - **Initial Coding** - Meaningful excerpts were tagged based on recurring themes.
 - **Theme Development** - Codes were grouped into broader thematic categories, such as "creative agency," "bias concerns," "collaborative potential," or "access barriers."
 - **Validation** - Two researchers independently coded the material and met to resolve discrepancies, ensuring reliability.
 - **Validation with stakeholder workshop** - An online workshop was organised to cluster and prioritise insights from the questionnaire.
 - **Translation to Stakeholder Design Requirements** - The resulting themes were mapped onto design requirements using HAMLET's shared criteria.

This approach ensured that user feedback was not abstracted into general usability data but remained grounded in the artistic, ethical, and performative realities of creative practice. In particular, responses were linked to the three methodological layers of HAMLET:

- **Value-Sensitive Design:** Emphasizing values like artistic authorship, fairness, and explainability.
- **Critical Making:** Identifying systemic concerns (e.g., exclusion, cultural erasure, platform dependency).
- **Users-as-Designers:** Capturing context-specific preferences, roles, and workflow requirements.

Together, this survey methodology provided an inclusive, participatory process that respects the multiplicity of voices within the CCI landscape and ensures that AI systems emerging from HAMLET are grounded in stakeholder needs, values, and constraints.

4.6.2 Results from the Survey and Workshop

To ensure that the HAMLET project reflects the lived realities and creative expectations of cultural and creative professionals, a stakeholder survey and validation workshop were conducted as central components of the requirement-gathering process. These activities form the backbone of Annex #4 and contributed significantly to the finalised stakeholder design requirements.

The survey was co-designed using a value-sensitive and qualitative methodology, grounded in real-world practices across key CCI domains—dance, theatre, gaming, and media art. Participants were asked not only about their current creative workflows and experience with AI tools, but also about their needs, concerns, and values in relation to the use of generative AI in their practices.

Distributed widely across partner networks, the survey received 125 responses, of which 45 surpassed the 60% completion threshold. Its structure balanced quantitative and qualitative components, enabling both trend analysis and deeper insight into sector-specific needs. Thematic coding of open responses—validated by multiple researchers—surfaced key themes such as creative agency, data consent, inclusivity, collaboration, cultural specificity, and transparency.

An online stakeholder workshop was organised to validate and enrich the survey findings. In this setting, stakeholders prioritised core issues and contributed further context, coalescing individual viewpoints into collectively recognised design directions. The final set of design requirements was thus not only extracted from raw data but shaped through participatory interpretation and discussion.

This combined process ensured that the resulting design requirements are not abstract checklists, but grounded reflections of the diversity, complexity, and aspirations of the communities HAMLET aims to serve.

The stakeholder survey and workshop revealed a clear, shared demand for human-centred, transparent, and ethically grounded AI systems that align with the creative realities of artists, designers, and cultural practitioners. The following insights summarise the most salient concerns and expectations voiced by participants.

- **Human creativity must remain central:** Artists strongly emphasized that generative AI should never replace authorship, expression, or the embodied dimensions of creative work. Instead, AI should assist with structuring, exploring, or expanding artistic processes while keeping the human at the centre. As one theatre director put it: “AI should never replace the artist. It can help with patterns, structures, or suggestions—but I am the one telling the story.”
- **Transparency and trust are essential for adoption:** Participants consistently demanded that AI systems offer understandable logic, traceable steps, and the ability to guide or override outputs.

Opaque, black-box systems were seen as undermining co-creation. In the words of a game developer: “I want to know why the AI made this choice-what data it saw, what logic it followed. Otherwise, I can’t trust it.”

- **Consent and data ownership are non-negotiable:** Stakeholders voiced concern over the unauthorized use of their creative work for model training. There was strong advocacy for opt-in frameworks and the right to withdraw consent. A choreographer expressed this plainly: “My work should not be used to train AI without my permission. That’s not collaboration-that’s theft.”
- **Cultural diversity must be reflected in outputs:** Participants warned against homogenization and the reproduction of dominant (Western, white, male) aesthetics. Instead, AI systems must support plural, situated, and minority perspectives. One performer and activist noted: “So much of what AI generates looks and sounds the same-Western, generic, smooth. Where is the weirdness? The local? The queer?”
- **Accessibility is vital to inclusive participation:** The need for intuitive, low-barrier tools was frequently mentioned, particularly by artists without technical backgrounds. A freelance artist shared: “I’m not a coder. If I need a developer to even try the tool, then it’s not for me.”
- **Infrastructure affects autonomy:** Artists expressed concern over dependence on centralised, subscription-based platforms that may not align with long-term sustainability or creative control. A digital theatre collective member remarked: “We shouldn’t be forced into using tools tied to Big Tech subscriptions. We need modular, sustainable systems we can install ourselves.”
- **Emotion, embodiment, and narrative depth must not be flattened:** Participants called for AI systems that can handle ambiguity, affect, and the unfinished qualities of live performance. This was especially emphasized in dance and theatre domains, where one performer noted: “The glitch, the stutter, the unfinished-these are part of how we perform. AI that smooths everything out is aesthetically boring.”
- **Co-creation is more valuable than automation:** Rather than accelerating production, creatives envision AI as a responsive partner-one that reflects, challenges, or extends their thinking. As one game designer explained: “I don’t want AI to replace my thinking. I want it to reflect how I think-so I can question it, or push it further.”

Table 11: General stakeholder requirements from the survey and workshop.

Design requirement	Description
Keep Human Creativity Central	AI should support-not replace-artistic authorship, improvisation, and narrative control. Outputs must preserve originality and embodied meaning.
AI as Creative Assistant	AI should act as a co-creator, offering variations or inspiration, without taking over the creative process.
Encourage Play & Experimentation	Tools must support misuse, play, error, and serendipity, leaving room for the unexpected.
Interactive Narrative Tools	In games and digital storytelling, AI should enable modular, branching, and user-curated narratives.
Style Transfer & Variation Explorer	Artists should be able to experiment with stylistic diversity, guided by aesthetic or conceptual intent.
Ensure Explainability	AI outputs must include traceable steps, visible reasoning, and editable parameters. Users should never encounter black-box results.
Cross-Sector Transparency & Governance	Systems must provide visible rules, model assumptions, and allow opt-outs for data sharing and training.

Support AI Literacy & Education	Tools should actively teach users how AI works, what biases exist, and how to interpret results.
Provide Step-by-Step Control	Users should be able to intervene at key stages: prompt negotiation, style guidance, or rejection of outputs.
Embodied Dialogue & Co-Creation	AI should work with motion data (e.g., Laban, mocap), allowing somatic interaction and multi-modal integration.
Protect Embodied & Situated Practices	AI must support-not abstract away from-physical presence, sensory inputs, and live contexts.
Multi-Modal Integration	Allow for creative mappings across media (e.g., sound ↔ motion, data ↔ visuals) to support hybrid workflows.
Support Diversity & Cultural Specificity	Avoid algorithmic bias and support underrepresented voices, aesthetics, and epistemologies.
Cultural Sensitivity & Respect	Prevent stereotypical outputs and encourage culturally situated responses and representation.
Foster Emotional & Narrative Depth	Support ambiguity, contradiction, and narrative richness in generated results. Avoid flattening affect.
Enable Accessibility for Non-Technical Creatives	No-code interfaces and intuitive workflows should enable wide artistic engagement.
Technical Interoperability	Tools must work across file formats, platforms, and production environments.
Local Infrastructure & Platform Independence	Avoid subscription models and enable local or open-source deployment.
Economic Accessibility	Micro-payment and non-subscription alternatives should be offered for equitable access.
Respect Consent & IP Rights	No reuse of data or style without consent. IP ownership must be acknowledged and preserved.
Ensure Data Sovereignty	Users must control how their data is stored, used, and whether it's included in AI training.
Cross-Sector Ethical Governance	Systemic rules for transparency, bias monitoring, and algorithmic accountability should be built-in.
Prioritize Environmental Sustainability	Systems should be lightweight and transparent about energy/resource usage.
Design for Longevity	Models must remain functional over time. Avoid hidden obsolescence tied to commercial updates.

5 Demographics

Geographical representation of involved stakeholders from chapters 4.2, 4.3 and 4.5. Pioneers and contemporary artists (Chapter 4.2) were primarily selected based on geographic diversity from different continents. Interviewees (Chapter 4.3) were selected based on their cultural background, many of them with dual country representation. Survey participants (Chapter 4.5) responded on project partner's newsletters and social media posts.

Figure 3. Geographical representation.

Gender diversity is represented almost half-half between male and female, few non-binaries, and some preferring not to disclose their gender.

Figure 4. Gender diversity.

Occupational status of engaged stakeholders varies mainly between **interdisciplinary and media arts** as primary domains of AI related arts, with **performance and gaming** as primary focus of HAMLET project, and various **media and creative research** domains. Many of involved stakeholders have multiple status, for example as artists and researchers.

Figure 5. Occupational status.

6 Conclusion & next steps

This deliverable has outlined a comprehensive approach to understanding stakeholder needs, identifying design constraints, and specifying requirements for human-centred AI tools in the Cultural and Creative Industries (CCIs). The methodology combined desk research, surveys, workshops, and direct engagements with artists, technologists, and other stakeholders, culminating in a robust framework of concerns, values, and design requirements.

The analysis identified **27 concerns** and **22 value commitments**, which were systematically mapped to **45 design requirements**. These, in turn, were evaluated against the project's overarching **general** and **pilot and enabler specific goals**, ensuring conceptual and operational alignment across the HAMLET framework.

Key insights include:

- A broad demand for **human-in-the-loop creative control**, resisting automation that displaces authorship or erodes artistic identity.
- The necessity of **explainability, transparency, and ethical reflexivity** in AI systems to build trust between users and developers, and protect creative autonomy.
- Strong emphasis on **inclusivity, accessibility, and cultural sensitivity**, particularly to counteract biases and prevent the marginalisation of underrepresented groups.
- The call for AI tools to support **co-creation, improvisation, and performative use**, especially in domains where embodied, time-based, or narrative expression is central.
- Cross-cutting concerns such as **data governance, environmental sustainability, and platform dependency** surfaced repeatedly, pointing to broader systemic issues that AI design must address.

The structured mapping exercise between concerns, values, and design requirements not only ensures internal coherence across the HAMLET objectives, but also provides a clear foundation for the next phases of framework and enablers development, pilot implementation, evaluation, validation, and final acceptance of project results by targeted stakeholders.

To ensure that the identified design requirements are not only conceptual but actionable, their implementation will be embedded across specific tasks in the HAMLET work plan. The rest of the WP1 will further detail functional and technical requirements specific for Pilots and Enablers, WP2 and WP3 will operationalize them through the development of enablers, while WP4 and WP5 will integrate sector-specific needs from pilots in dance, theatre, and games. WP6 will ensure alignment with ethical, cultural, and policy frameworks by monitoring the uptake of non-functional requirements such as transparency, inclusivity, and sustainability. Furthermore, WP7 will test feasibility through real-world validation with creative users, using iterative evaluation loops, usability testing, and feedback collection.

Critical for next steps is **involvement of actual creative users into iterative design and development of enablers**-as one of more processual requirements from involved stakeholders-with **creative challenges emerging from creative practice, concerns related to concrete creative practice and specific interactions with audiences, and values specific for selected creative and cultural contexts**, from general avoidance of bias to actual care for authenticity and different creative and personal identities. Involvement of creative users in design and development **contributes also to expected acceptance of project results**, first by pilots as primary users and second by CCI community that trusts tools and technologies developed within the community.

In terms of feasibility, most design requirements are technically achievable within the scope of HAMLET, though their complexity varies. Human-in-the-loop control, iterative prompt negotiation, and transparency mechanisms can be implemented with existing interaction design and explainability methods. More advanced requirements-such as embodied interaction, cultural sensitivity in data, or long-term sustainability of infrastructures-pose greater challenges. These will require close collaboration between creative users (Pilots) and technologists (Enablers), careful dataset curation, and iterative ethical oversight. The project's phased approach-concept design, iterative prototyping, pilot validation, and evaluation-provides the structure needed to address feasibility in practice, balancing technical ambition with practical adoption.

Beside the stakeholder requirements for design and development of Enablers and Pilots, this deliverable also provides foundations for development of Collaborative Community Hub (T4.2) and Virtual Living Lab (T6.1) as platforms for further engagement with project stakeholders. General stakeholder requirement topics (Chapter 4.1) will be further discussed between project partners and targeted stakeholders based on concrete creative and technical challenges.

In sum, the design requirements outlined in this deliverable provide a coherent foundation for the HAMLET project's ambition to shape human-centred, value-driven AI in the cultural and creative industries. By embedding these requirements into concrete tasks, testing their feasibility through iterative pilot activities, and addressing risks through adaptive governance, HAMLET ensures that its outcomes are not only technically sound but also ethically robust and culturally relevant. This alignment between vision, requirements, and implementation marks a decisive step toward building AI systems that amplify creative agency and safeguard cultural diversity, while setting a reference point for future European innovation at the intersection of art, technology, and society.

References

- [1] Amy Goodchild. n.d. 'Early Computer Art in the 50's & 60's'. Accessed 19 September 2025. <https://www.amygoodchild.com/blog/computer-art-50s-and-60s>
- [2] 'An Interview with Vera Molnar'. n.d. Accessed 19 September 2025. <https://www.rightclick-save.com/article/an-interview-with-vera-molnar>
- [3] Crawford, Kate, and Vladan Joler. 2018. 'Anatomy of an AI System'. Anatomy of an AI System. <http://www.anatomyof.ai>.
- [4] *Drawing Operations (2015) - Sougwen Chung (愷君)*. n.d. Accessed 19 September 2025. <https://sougwen.com/project/drawing-operations>
- [5] Dreher, Thomas. 2020a. *History of Computer Art*. Lulu.com.
- [6] Dreher, Thomas. 2020b. *History of Computer Art*. 2nd update June 2020 for the eBook, with A modified chapter II.1.1. Lulu Press. <https://doi.org/10.11588/artdok.00007723>
- [7] Friedman, Batya, Peter H. Kahn, Alan Borning, and Alina Huldtgren. 2013. 'Value Sensitive Design and Information Systems'. In *Early Engagement and New Technologies: Opening up the Laboratory*, edited by Neelke Doorn, Daan Schuurbijs, Ibo van de Poel, and Michael E. Gorman. Springer Netherlands. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-007-7844-3_4
- [8] Futurelab, Waag. n.d.-a. 'The Role of Critical Making'. InteractiveResource. Waag Futurelab, Waag Futurelab. Accessed 19 September 2025. <https://waag.org/en/article/role-critical-making/>.
- [9] Futurelab, Waag. n.d.-b. 'Users as Designers'. InteractiveResource. Waag Futurelab, Waag Futurelab. Accessed 19 September 2025. <https://waag.org/en/project/users-designers/>
- [10] 'Gordon Pask's MusiColour Machine'. n.d. *Imager by Rhythmic Light*®. Accessed 19 September 2025. <https://rhythmiclight.com/timeline/gordon-pasks-musicolour-machine/>
- [11] IT museum DataArt. n.d. 'Random Dances in Cybernetic Serendipity'. DataArt IT Museum. Accessed 19 September 2025. <https://museum.dataart.com/short-stories/random-dances-in-cybernetic-serendipity>.
- [12] *New SME & Artist Collaboration Guide Launched by Better Factory to Transform European Manufacturing | Better Factory*. 2024. News. August 22. <https://betterfactory.eu/new-sme-artist-collaboration-guide-launched-by-better-factory-to-transform-european-manufacturing/>
- [13] Pask, Gordon. n.d. *A Comment, a Case History and a Plan*.
- [14] 'Public Stack'. n.d. Accessed 19 September 2025. <https://publicstack.net/>
- [15] Shroff, Lila. 2022. 'Datasets as Imagination'. May 22. <https://joinreboot.org/p/artist-datasets>
- [16] 'Spacewar! | PDP-1 Restoration Project | Computer History Museum'. n.d. Accessed 19 September 2025. <https://www.computerhistory.org/pdp-1/spacewar/>
- [17] The New Real. n.d. 'The New Real | Open Prototyping'. Accessed 19 September 2025. <https://www.newreal.cc/openprototyping>
- [18] *Wikipedia* 2024. 'AARON'. <https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=AARON&oldid=1255090049>, Nov. 3.

